

EÖTVÖS LORÁND UNIVERSITY
FACULTY OF INFORMATICS

THE ART OF CONDENSATION:
CONSTRUCTING A STATE-OF-THE-ART
MULTILINGUAL SUMMARIZATION DATASET

ANDRÁS BENCZÚR
PROFESSOR AT ELTE
ANDREA PASSERINI
ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR AT UNITN
MÁRTON MIHÁLTZ
PRINCIPAL MACHINE LEARNING ENGINEER AT
MELTWATER

PATRICK NANYS
COMPUTER SCIENCE

BUDAPEST, 2024.

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I hereby confirm the submission of the Master Thesis Work on the Computer Science Msc course with author and title:

Name of Student: Patrick Nanys

Neptun ID of the Student: D3QVKO

Title of Thesis: The Art of Condensation: Constructing a State-of-the-Art Multilingual Summarization Dataset

Supervisor: András Benczúr

at Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Infomatics.

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Nanys Patrick
student

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MASTER THESIS TOPIC DECLARATION FORM

Name of Student: Patrick Nanys

Neptun code: D3QVKO

Training: Full-time

Technical major: Data Science

Email Address: patrick.nanys2000@gmail.com

Phone Number: +36 70 226 5105

Name of ELTE supervisor: András Benczúr

Workplace: Eötvös Loránd University

Name of Exit-university supervisor: Andrea Passerini

Workplace: University of Trento

Name of Industrial supervisor: Márton Miháltz

Workplace: Meltwater Kft.

Information about the internship

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Weekly schedule:

- Week 1 (2024-02-26 - 2024-03-03): Orientation and introduction to the project and team.

The purpose of the admission declaration is to certify that the student of the MSc in Computer Science at ELTE Faculty of Informatics may complete the mandatory internship in the selected institution within the framework detailed hereby and in accordance with the learning outcomes required by the program.

- Week 2 (2024-03-04 - 2024-03-10): Training on Elasticsearch and data extraction techniques.
- Week 3 (2024-03-11 - 2024-03-17): Begin extracting data and initial dataset creation.
- Week 4 (2024-03-18 - 2024-03-24): Implement data cleaning and preprocessing algorithms.
- Week 5 (2024-03-25 - 2024-03-31): Apply text similarity measures and refine dataset.
- Week 6 (2024-04-01 - 2024-04-07): Develop and test junk data clustering method.
- Week 7 (2024-04-08 - 2024-04-14): Evaluate and optimize data processing workflows.
- Week 8 (2024-04-15 - 2024-04-21): Manual quality checks for dataset validation.
- Week 9 (2024-04-22 - 2024-04-28): Prepare the dataset for multilingual summarization model training.
- Week 10 (2024-04-29 - 2024-05-05): Conduct preliminary tests with summarization models.
- Week 11 (2024-05-06 - 2024-05-12): Analyze test results and refine the dataset accordingly.
- Week 12 (2024-05-13 - 2024-05-19): Finalize the dataset and documentation for release.
- Week 13 (2024-05-20 - 2024-05-27): Present project results and conclusions to the team.

Title of the thesis

The Art of Condensation: Constructing a State-of-the-Art Multilingual Summarization Dataset

Topic of the thesis (1 – 1,5 pages)

- **Context and Motivation:** In the digital age, the ability to succinctly summarize extensive texts is increasingly important for improving content accessibility and understanding. As the volume of online content, especially news articles, grows exponentially, there is a pressing demand for advanced summarization technologies. This project aims to address the critical shortage of high-quality, diverse summarization datasets that are essential for training sophisticated machine learning models, focusing on enhancing resources for multilingual summarization and improving text summarization methodologies.
- **What would you like to achieve (Added value):** My objective is to create a distinctive, comprehensive summarization dataset characterized by its extensive volume, impeccable quality, and broad linguistic range. This dataset will be meticulously compiled from a large corpus of news articles, ensuring that each selection meets our criteria for relevance and diversity. The project is particularly focused on including content in multiple languages, aiming to significantly extend the dataset's applicability and usefulness in global summarization efforts. An essential part of this project involves implementing sophisticated data cleaning and processing techniques to remove common flaws like duplication and crawling-induced errors. A novel approach will be to design and utilize an advanced method for automatically clustering junk data, recognizing that manual inspection is impractical due to the dataset's vast size. By refining the process for matching summaries to their corresponding content, the dataset will facilitate the training of summarization algorithms capable of generating authentic summaries rather than mere content snippets. This initiative seeks to propel the development of AI summarization algorithms that closely emulate human summarization skills across various languages, pushing the envelope of AI's ability to understand and succinctly summarize extensive texts.
- **Research Questions:**

- How can advanced data cleaning and automatic clustering methods be designed and applied to efficiently segregate and eliminate junk data from a terabyte-scale dataset?
- What innovative strategies can be developed to enhance text similarity measures, ensuring the differentiation of genuine summaries from simple content extracts and improving the dataset's value for summarization model training?
- How can the dataset be structured to support a diverse array of languages, fostering inclusivity and broadening the impact of AI-powered summarization tools?
- **How would you like to achieve this (Methodology):**
 - The foundation of this project is the strategic use of the company's in house Elasticsearch cluster to source data, with carefully formulated queries to collect news articles suitable for summarization. Given the enormity of the dataset, distributed computing frameworks like Apache Spark will be pivotal for efficient data processing. Advanced data cleaning will involve not only traditional NLP techniques for text preprocessing but also the development of a sophisticated algorithm for automatically clustering and removing junk data, ensuring the dataset's cleanliness and relevance.
 - To guarantee the integrity of the summaries, advanced algorithms or machine learning models will be employed to compute text similarity, effectively distinguishing between actual summaries and mere introductory content. This step will include creating or enhancing text similarity algorithms to accommodate multilingual content and scale efficiently with the dataset's size.
 - Additionally, the project will incorporate manual quality checks for a subset of the data to ensure unmatched accuracy and relevance. Metadata, including language tags, will annotate the dataset entries, enhancing its utility for developing summarization models across different languages.
 - The project will leverage a variety of technologies and tools, including Elasticsearch for data retrieval, Apache Spark for distributed data processing, and NLP libraries for text processing and similarity analysis. This comprehensive approach aims to produce a valuable resource for the research community, contributing significantly to the advancement of summarization technologies.

- **5 Keywords:**

- Summarization Dataset
- Multilingual Text Processing
- Junk Data Clustering
- Text Similarity Measures
- Distributed Data Processing

Encryption of the topic is necessary: YES/NO

I approve of the suggested topic of the Master's Thesis:

Budapest, 02.19.2024

ELTE supervisor

I approve of the suggested topic of the Master's Thesis:

Budapest, 02.19.2024

Exit-university supervisor

I approve of the suggested topic of the internship, and in the name of the institution (organization, company) above I agree, that the named student will carry out his/her internship along the conditions detailed above:

Budapest, 02.19.2024

Industrial supervisor

I ask for the acceptance of my thesis topic.

Budapest, 02.20.2024

Student

The topic of the thesis and internship is approved by the EIT Digital Program Lead of ELTE Faculty of Informatics

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o=Eötvös Loránd
Tudományegyetem, title=ELTE IK
Informatikatudományi Intézet
igazgató, sn=Dr. Horváth,
givenName=Zoltán,
serialNumber=DO20200616-1DO
8, cn=Dr. Horváth Zoltán
2024.02.21 12:51:09 +01'00'

Dr. Horváth Zoltán
EIT Digital Program Lead

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In the field of natural language processing (NLP), the development of sophisticated models capable of understanding and generating text across a diverse array of languages is paramount. This is particularly true in the domain of abstractive summarization, where the ability to distill complex content into concise summaries is not only a technological challenge but also a linguistic one. The creation of multilingual datasets that can support the training of such models is critical, yet existing datasets often fall short in terms of both scope and depth. For instance, the XL-SUM dataset [HBI⁺21], while currently the largest for multilingual abstractive summarization with its coverage of 44 languages and over one million annotated article-summary pairs, does not encompass several significant high-resource languages such as Hungarian, Italian and German. Moreover, it typically provides only a few thousand samples per language, insufficient for deep learning models that require large amounts of data to achieve optimal performance.

Given these limitations, the aim of this paper is to address the need for a new, expansive multilingual dataset specifically tailored for abstractive summarization. Unlike prior efforts which often focus on expanding or refining existing datasets, this project proposes the construction of a completely new dataset from the ground up, one that includes a broad range of both high-resource and low-resource languages while ensuring a substantial volume of data for each. Accompanying the dataset, a novel model for abstractive summarization will be developed, designed to leverage this rich linguistic diversity effectively.

This initiative will involve the collection of sources, ensuring linguistic diversity and representativeness, and overcoming challenges associated with the cleaning in certain languages. The expected result is a balanced, comprehensive dataset that not only fills the current gaps in language coverage but also supports the development of more advanced, equitable summarization technologies. By fostering better performance across a wide spectrum of languages, this project aims to set a new standard in multilingual NLP, facilitating

more accurate and culturally relevant summarizations that enhance understanding and accessibility worldwide.

Meltwater [mel] is a premier international provider of media intelligence and social analytics. This organization systematically processes hundreds of millions of documents daily, sourced from a diverse array of online platforms including blogs, forums, news articles, and social media postings. These documents undergo enhancement through several sophisticated algorithms that facilitate language detection, sentiment analysis, content classification, and author qualification. Over the years, Meltwater has amassed a substantial repository of ingresses—concise summaries that encapsulate the essence of editorial content—from web pages of leading news outlets such as the BBC. These ingresses, often authored by the original writers of the articles, represent a multilingual collection due to Meltwater’s comprehensive web coverage. Despite their inherent imperfections, these data samples hold significant potential for advancing the state of the art in multilingual abstractive summarization. If leveraged effectively, Meltwater’s rich datasets could markedly enhance performance in multilingual summarization tasks.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 NLP Foundations

This chapter reviews the progression of tokenization in NLP, detailing the shift from simple text segmentation methods to advanced, trainable tokenizers. It begins by defining the tokenization process, essential for NLP accuracy, then critiques the basic Bag-of-words (BoW) model for its limitations in complex linguistic analysis. Finally, it highlights modern tokenizers that leverage deep learning to efficiently handle multilingual texts, reflecting significant advances in NLP technology.

2.1.1 Tokenization

Documents can be envisioned as a sequence of symbols, represented as $[X_i]_{i \in \{1, \dots, T\}}$ where each X_i is an element of a set V , defined as $V = v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n$. This set, known as the vocabulary, varies by language and may consist of alphabetic characters or logographic symbols. Typically, it is more effective to use words or sub-words as units of linguistic analysis, known as tokens. The process known as tokenization involves dividing unstructured text into these meaningful units. Consider the term “summarization”, which could be tokenized into individual characters [“s”, “u”, “m”, “m”, “a”, “r”, “i”, “z”, “a”, “t”, “i”, “o”, “n”], into components [“summar”, “ization”], or as a single unit [“summarization”]. The choice of tokenization method is vital in NLP, as the sequential nature of text necessitates breaking it down into tokens, significantly impacting the performance of NLP models.

2.1.2 Bag-of-words

Tokenization is a fundamental process in every NLP algorithm, as the method of tokenization varies depending on the intended use of the text. For instance, the bag-of-words

(BoW) model, introduced by [Har54] in 1954, simplifies the vectorization of text by tokenizing it into individual words and then counting each word’s occurrences within the text. This allows a document to be represented as a BoW vector, facilitating the comparison of vectors among documents. However, this model does not preserve the order of tokens.

Despite its simplicity and effectiveness, the BoW model exhibits several limitations. It often results in high frequencies of common words, lacks sensitivity to word order, and can lead to issues with vocabulary and vector size in large document corpora. Additionally, the model’s sparse nature and its inability to compare words that are lexically or grammatically similar further complicate its application in more nuanced linguistic analyses.

2.1.3 Trained Tokenizers

Modern NLP applications increasingly require the capability to handle texts from multiple languages, necessitating the use of trainable, language-agnostic tokenizers. Traditionally, tokenization relied on rules-based and vocabulary-based methods, which utilized language-specific lists of stop-words and stemming rules. However, these methods are not suited for the multilingual and dynamic nature of language usage today, particularly with the advent of deep learning which favors models that learn from raw data.

In response to these needs, trained tokenizers such as Byte-Pair-Encoding (BPE), unigram language models, and SentencePiece have become prevalent. BPE, initially developed as a data compression algorithm, has been adapted for NLP to encode rare words by iteratively merging frequent pairs of characters into single tokens, thus allowing for efficient encoding of large vocabularies [SHB15]. Similarly, the unigram language model [Kud18] and SentencePiece, which combines BPE with the unigram approach [KR18], are subword tokenizers that create vocabularies iteratively from extensive text corpora. These advanced tokenizers are capable of processing almost any sentence without generating unknown tokens, exemplifying the neural network paradigm where machines learn autonomously from vast amounts of data.

2.2 Neural Networks Literature

2.2.1 Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [RHW86] represent a sophisticated deep learning methodology tailored for the analysis of sequential data. Prior to the emergence of attention mechanisms, RNNs were predominantly recommended for tasks involving such data. In contrast to deep feedforward models, which may necessitate distinct parameters

for each sequence element and struggle with generalization across sequences of varying lengths, RNNs employ uniform weights across all elements. This uniformity not only reduces the parameter count but also enhances the model’s ability to adapt to sequences of different lengths.

Neural networks are computational models that mimic the operational principles of the human brain, facilitating pattern recognition and problem-solving within the realms of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning. RNNs, a derivative of feed-forward networks, epitomize this by modeling sequential data effectively. These networks display similarities to human cognitive processes in their ability to predict outcomes based on sequential input, a capability that sets them apart from other algorithms.

Traditional neural networks handle inputs and outputs as discrete, independent entities. However, certain tasks, such as predicting subsequent words in a sentence, require an awareness of previous inputs. To address this, RNNs incorporate a hidden layer that retains relevant past information, thus enabling sequential data processing. The core feature of an RNN is its hidden state, which serves as a memory bank, storing all pertinent details through the sequence of computations. This memory allows the RNN to apply consistent settings across each input, facilitating uniform outputs across different inputs or hidden layers.

However, RNNs also exhibit certain disadvantages that can limit their effectiveness. A prominent issue is their susceptibility to the vanishing and exploding gradient problems [BSF94], which can severely impede the learning process. Training RNNs, particularly on long sequences, can be complex and resource-intensive. Furthermore, they are often computationally slower compared to other neural network architectures, which may constrain their use in time-sensitive applications.

2.2.2 Long Short-Term Memory Networks

Long Short Term Memory networks, commonly abbreviated as LSTMs, represent a specialized variant of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) that are adept at learning long-term dependencies. Originally introduced by [HS97] in 1997, LSTMs have undergone considerable refinement and popularization through subsequent research. These networks have demonstrated remarkable efficacy across a diverse array of problems and have become a staple in the field due to their robustness.

Designed specifically to circumvent the long-term dependency problem, LSTMs inherently maintain information over prolonged periods, effortlessly embodying this capability as a core feature rather than an acquired skill. Unlike standard RNNs, which are characterized by a simple, repetitive module structure typified by a single tanh layer, LSTMs

employ a more complex arrangement. Within their chain-like framework, the repetitive module comprises four distinct neural network layers that interact in a uniquely intricate manner.

The initial phase in the operation of a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) network involves determining the information to be discarded from the cell state. This process is governed by a sigmoid layer known as the “forget gate layer”, which assesses both h_{t-1} and x_t , and generates a value between 0 and 1 for each element in the cell state C_{t-1} . Here, a value of 1 signifies complete retention, whereas a value of 0 indicates total removal.

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f)$$

Subsequently, the network decides the new information to be incorporated into the cell state. This decision occurs in two stages: initially, a sigmoid layer, termed the “input gate layer”, selects the values to be updated; following this, a tanh layer proposes a vector of new candidate values, $\tilde{C}_t$, which might be added to the state. These components are then merged to update the state.

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C)$$

The next step involves transitioning from the old cell state, C_{t-1} , to the new cell state, C_t . This update is executed by multiplying the old state by f_t , thereby omitting the previously designated elements for deletion, and subsequently adding $i_t * \tilde{C}_t$, where the new candidate values are scaled by the extent to which each state value is to be updated.

$$C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t$$

The final stage entails determining the output based on the cell state, albeit in a filtered manner. Initially, a sigmoid layer is employed to select the aspects of the cell state to be outputted. This is followed by processing the cell state through a tanh function (normalizing values to the range $[-1, 1]$), and multiplying the result by the output from the sigmoid gate to selectively output the designated parts.

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$$

$$h_t = o_t * \tanh(C_t)$$

Figure 2.1: Long Short Term Memory (LSTM); image from [mlb]

2.2.3 Sequence to Sequence Models

The introductory section on sequential models revealed their intrinsic ability to map input sequences to fixed-size vectors, and reciprocally, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) can map an input sequence to an output sequence of the same length. Nonetheless, such fixed relationships between input and output lengths significantly limit their utility in real-world applications. Many complex tasks such as question answering, speech recognition, and machine translation require models that manage input and output sequences of varying lengths. This essay delves into how recurrent neural networks can be used to navigate the mapping between sequences of dissimilar lengths, utilizing what are known as sequence-to-sequence models or encoder-decoder networks [SVL14, CVMG⁺14].

The core concept underlying sequence-to-sequence models is relatively straightforward yet powerful. The encoder in these models ingests an input sequence and encodes it into a dense vector representation, often termed the 'context vector'. This vector serves as a compressed representation of the semantic content of the input sequence. It is then used as the starting point for the decoder, which is tasked with producing the output sequence, token by token. This process allows for the generation of an output sequence that may not necessarily match the input in length, accommodating the requirements of various applications that demand flexible sequence lengths.

Formally, if input sequence is denoted as $(x_1, \dots, x_{\hat{T}})$ and the corresponding output sequence as $(y_1, \dots, y_T)$, the process of sequence generation in a sequence-to-sequence architecture can be succinctly described by the following probability model:

$$p(y_1, \dots, y_T | x_1, \dots, x_{\hat{T}}) = \prod_{t=1}^{\hat{T}} p(y_t | v, y_1, \dots, y_{t-1})$$

Here, v represents the context vector derived from the input sequence by the encoder. This formula captures the essence of how each output token is generated sequentially, dependent on the context vector and all preceding output tokens.

It is crucial to note the potential disparity in sequence lengths, denoted by T and $\hat{T}$. This flexibility is a significant advantage over traditional RNNs that output sequences of fixed lengths. The training of these sequence-to-sequence models is accomplished by optimizing a log-likelihood objective, typically expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{S} \sum_{T,S \in S} \log(p(T|S))$$

where S symbolizes the training set comprising pairs of source (input) and target (output) sequences. The optimization of this objective function is achieved through backpropagation through time, which is adaptable across the entire model. This method ensures that the encoder and decoder weights are optimally adjusted to maximize the probability of the target sequence given the input sequence, often employing optimization techniques such as stochastic gradient descent.

For example, inputs A, B, and C are fed into the encoder, producing output tokens W, X, Y, and Z sequentially in the decoder. The strategic use of the $\langle \text{eos} \rangle$ (end of sentence) token is critical as it facilitates the generation of sequences that can variably end depending on the context and sequence dynamics.

The actual process of generating output sequences from the distribution of possible words includes several strategies. A straightforward approach is to take the output from the softmax function, which provides probabilities for each possible output token, and select the token with the highest probability. This method is deterministic, leading to the same output sequence given the same input sequence. However, this approach does not guarantee that the sequence produced is the optimal one. An alternative method involves stochastic decoding, such as using Roulette Wheel Selection [Mit98], where each token is probabilistically selected based on its computed likelihood at each timestep. Though feasible, it is often more effective to perform decoding in a batch process, where the entire sequence corresponding to the highest cumulative probability is chosen at once. Below is an equation representing the above where S is the source and T is the target sequence.

$$\hat{T} = \max_T p(T|S)$$

A significant challenge arises from the encoder's limited capacity to fully encapsulate the extensive semantic information of an input sequence into a singular, fixed-dimension context vector. This limitation often hampers the model's ability to accurately reflect

Figure 2.2: Beam search (source: [Top])

the nuanced meaning of the input in its output. To mitigate this issue, the concept of the context vector, typically denoted as v , is reimaged from a static, fixed-size vector to a dynamic, variable-length sequence. This adaptation allows for a more flexible representation of the input sequence’s content. Additionally, the integration of the attention mechanism plays a pivotal role in enhancing these architectures by enabling the model to dynamically learn and emphasize the associations between specific elements of the context vector and corresponding segments of the output sequence.

The decoding process in practical sequence-to-sequence applications is critically influenced by the inherent computational complexity involved in identifying the optimal sequence. An exhaustive search across all possible sequences would require computational resources that scale exponentially with the length of the output sequence, making such an approach impractical for real-world applications. To work around this computational bottleneck, most systems employ a left-to-right beam search strategy [Gra12], which is visualized in Figure 2.2. This technique involves a key hyperparameter known as the beam size, represented by k . During the initial decoding step, the model retains k tokens that exhibit the highest conditional probabilities. These tokens then serve as the inaugural elements for k potential output sequences.

Subsequent steps involve a meticulous process where k tokens are selected iteratively at each timestep. This selection is based on their conditional probabilities, calculated in relation to the evolving k candidate sequences from the previous timesteps. Each step strategically narrows the potential choices by focusing only on the most promising contin-

uations based on the accumulated context from the input sequence and the partial output sequences generated thus far.

This structured approach to decoding effectively reduces the vast search space to a manageable subset of likely candidate sequences, thereby making the computational task tractable. The beam search not only provides a pragmatic balance between efficiency and the quality of the generated sequences but also ensures that the computational effort remains within feasible limits, even as the output sequence length increases.

The use of the attention mechanism in conjunction with the variable-length context vector significantly enhances the model’s performance. By allowing the decoder to focus selectively on different parts of the input sequence at different times, the attention mechanism ensures that the output sequences are not only coherent but also contextually appropriate. This targeted approach helps in better aligning the decoder’s outputs with the intended meanings and nuances captured in the input sequence, thereby improving the overall efficacy and adaptability of sequence-to-sequence models in handling complex sequence generation tasks across various domains such as machine translation, speech recognition, and automated response generation.

2.2.4 Attention

Neural Machine Translation (NMT) models predominantly employ an encoder-decoder architecture [SVL14, CVMG⁺14], which encapsulates the essential components for language translation. An inherent limitation of this structure is its reliance on a fixed-length vector to represent an entire source sentence, which complicates the model’s ability to encapsulate comprehensive semantic details from extended texts [GBC16]. This challenge is addressed by a novel extension proposed by [BCB16], which enhances the typical NMT framework.

This extended architecture integrates a bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (BiRNN) [SP97] in the encoder as can be seen in Figure 2.3. The BiRNN processes input word vectors through both forward and backward computations, generating concatenated hidden states for each word x_j , denoted as annotation a_j . These annotations $(a_1, \dots, a_{T_x})$ encapsulate contextual information from both preceding and subsequent words, providing a richer representation than conventional RNNs.

The decoding phase incorporates an attention mechanism facilitated by a multilayer perceptron (MLP) with a single hidden layer, functioning as an alignment model f . This model, trainable alongside the primary architecture, calculates the relevance e_{ij} of each annotation a_j with respect to the decoder’s previous state h_{i-1} as shown in Equation 2.1. The significance of each annotation is determined through a softmax function, yielding a weight α_{ij} for each annotation as expressed in Equation 2.2:

Figure 2.3: Bahdanau attention (source: [BCB16])

$$e_{ij} = f(h_{i-1}, a_j) \quad (2.1)$$

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp(e_{ij})}{\sum_{k=1}^{T_c} \exp(e_{ik})} \quad (2.2)$$

These weights inform the construction of a context vector c_i , a weighted aggregation of annotations, reflecting the decoder’s focus on specific segments of the input sentence relevant to generating the target word y_t . The resultant context vector c_i is computed as follows [BCB16]:

$$c_i = \sum_{j=1}^{T_x} \alpha_{ij} a_j \quad (2.3)$$

This adaptive selection mechanism mitigates the need to compress all source sentence information into a fixed-length vector, enabling the model to maintain and leverage a dynamic representation of the input throughout the translation process. Thus, the proposed modifications to the NMT architecture significantly enhance its capacity to manage long sentences by preserving intricate semantic nuances.

In [LPM15] two distinct attention mechanisms are touched upon in NMT: global and local. Global attention encompasses all source words throughout the process, forming a context vector c_t by considering every hidden state from the encoder. This approach generates a variable-length alignment vector akin to the formula depicted in Eq. 2.2, where the target hidden state h_t is evaluated against each source hidden state h_s using a scoring function rather than the associated energy e_{ij} . Consequently, an alignment vector, proportional in size to the time steps on the source side, is established. Using this vector as weights, c_t is calculated as the weighted mean of all source hidden states, where the score function acts as a content-based mechanism, with three variants under consideration.

Conversely, the local attention mechanism, which is inherently differentiable, operates by determining an aligned position p_t for each target word at time t . Subsequently, a window centered on p_t is employed to compute the context vector as a weighted average of the source hidden states within that specified window. This selective focus on a narrow window enables the derivation of the alignment vector from the current target state h_t and the source states h_s within the window, distinguishing it from the global method [LPM15].

2.2.5 The Transformer

The transformer model, initially recognized for its unparalleled performance in machine translation [VSP⁺17], has subsequently demonstrated its superiority across a diverse array of natural language processing (NLP) tasks [RWC⁺19, DCLT18]. This paper delves into the sophisticated architecture of the transformer, as illustrated in Figure 2.4. Comprising two principal sub-components, the encoder and the decoder networks, the transformer’s architecture is intricate. The encoder network processes the source sentence, converting it into a word embedding, and generates a comprehensive representation of the sentence. Utilizing this representation, in conjunction with the word embeddings of the previously generated tokens from the output sentence, the decoder then calculates the output probabilities for each subsequent word. The decoding process is inherently auto-regressive; each prediction relies on the words predicted prior to it. Moreover, Phuong and Hutter [PH22] provide a detailed formalization of the components unique to various transformer variants, along with pseudocode for their training and inference processes.

The encoder within a standard transformer architecture consists of six identical layers, arranged sequentially so that the output of one layer n becomes the input for the subsequent layer $n + 1$. Each of these layers is divided into two key components: a multi-head self-attention mechanism and a position-wise feed-forward network. Both components are enhanced with skip connections and are normalized at the layer level.

In parallel, the decoder’s structure mirrors that of the encoder, comprising similarly

Figure 2.4: Transformer model architecture

six layers. However, the internal composition of these layers varies slightly. A distinctive block, inserted between the multi-head self-attention and the position-wise linear blocks, facilitates a linkage with the encoder by implementing multi-head attention across the encoder's output. As previously indicated, the initial block in the decoder sequence integrates embeddings from previously generated tokens in the output sequence, adhering to an auto-regressive protocol. To maintain the integrity of this sequence generation, a masking technique is employed to ensure that future tokens do not influence the attention mechanism prematurely. Furthermore, the output embeddings are systematically shifted by one position to ensure that the prediction of any given token t is contingent solely upon the tokens that have been generated before it. This structured approach effectively maintains the sequential integrity and predictive accuracy of the transformer model.

Multi Head Attention

In the architecture of transformers, the mechanism of attention is delineated as a multi-head scaled dot-product operation, applied across q , k , and v , which stand for query, key, and value vectors respectively. These vectors are initially derived from input embeddings; each input undergoes a three part projection to generate the corresponding queries, keys, and values, all of which share the same dimensional attributes as the input.

The architecture also features self-attention blocks where these vectors are self-derived,

meaning each component is projected from the same input sequence. Contrastingly, in the interface between the encoder and decoder, known as the attention block, the query vectors originate from the projections of the decoder's preceding attention block outputs, while the keys and values are projected from the outputs of the final encoder layer. This complex interaction can be succinctly encapsulated in the subsequent mathematical representation:

$$\text{ScaledDotProductAttention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V$$

Here, d_k symbolizes the dimensionality of the key vectors, and Q , K , V are matrices formulated by concatenating q , k , and v across the sequence.

Furthermore, the transformer utilizes a multi-headed approach to attention, facilitating the concurrent computation of multiple attention processes on disparate segments of the input. This is achieved through linear projections that reduce the dimensionality of the Q , K , and V matrices, as represented in the following equation:

$$d_{\text{channel}} = \frac{d_{\text{input}}}{h}$$

In this expression, d_{input} represents the dimension of the input, and h denotes the number of attention heads. The dimension reduction for each head is operationalized via learned weight matrices, expressed as:

$$\text{head}_i = \text{ScaledDotProductAttention}(QW_{Q_i}, KW_{K_i}, VW_{V_i})$$

where W_{Q_i} , W_{K_i} , and W_{V_i} represent the learnable parameters corresponding to each head. Given an input sequence dimension of $d_{\text{input}} = 512$ and $h = 8$, the attention computation is distributed, conducted in parallel across segments of dimension $\frac{d_{\text{input}}}{h} = 64$.

Subsequently, the results from all heads are aggregated, concatenated, and projected to generate the final output of the attention block, as depicted in the equation below:

$$\text{MultiHeadAttention} = \text{Concatenate}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h)W_O$$

where W_O is the learned projection matrix for the output.

Other Components

The Feedforward Neural Network (FFN) within the transformer architecture plays a pivotal role in enhancing the model's ability to capture complex patterns and relationships. The FFN is composed of two linear transformations with a nonlinear activation function in between. Mathematically, it can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{W}_2\sigma(\mathbf{W}_1\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}_1) + \mathbf{b}_2$$

Where:

- $\mathbf{W}_1$ and $\mathbf{W}_2$ are the weight matrices.
- $\mathbf{b}_1$ and $\mathbf{b}_2$ are bias vectors.
- σ represents the activation function, such as ReLU or GELU.

The FFN operates independently on each position of the input sequence, ensuring that the same operations are applied to each position. This property allows the transformer to maintain its powerful ability to process sequences in parallel, significantly enhancing computational efficiency.

The primary function of the FFN is to transform input features into higher dimensional spaces and back, enabling the network to learn more complex abstractions. The nonlinear activation function introduces the necessary nonlinearity into the system, which is crucial for learning intricate data patterns that linear operations alone cannot achieve. By mapping input features to a higher-dimensional space, the FFN can disentangle and recombine features in ways that are non-trivial, thus increasing the model’s depth and capacity for feature representation.

In the context of the transformer architecture, the FFN is critical for adding depth to each layer. After the multi-head attention module computes attention scores and aggregates information across different positions of the input sequence, the FFN further processes this information by applying a series of transformations. The inclusion of residual connections around each sub-layer, followed by layer normalization, ensures that the FFN contributes effectively to the overall learning process without causing destabilization in training dynamics. The residual connections help in mitigating the vanishing gradient problem by allowing gradients to flow directly through the network’s layers.

To enhance the robustness of the architecture of transformers, a multitude of regularization techniques are strategically implemented. Notably, each layer’s output undergoes a normalization process known as layer normalization, which employs basic statistical metrics—specifically the mean and variance—calculated at the layer level [BKH16]. This normalization also extends across the residual connections that link the inputs and outputs of each layer, as delineated by the equation:

$$\text{LayerNorm}(X, \text{Sublayer}(X))$$

Here, X represents the input, while Sublayer denotes the function executed by the layer. Additionally, the transformer utilizes dropout, a stochastic regularization mechanism that randomly sets input elements to zero with a predetermined probability [SHK⁺14]. This technique is applied both prior to the layer normalization at each layer’s output and during the computation of the scaled dot-product, thereby enhancing the model’s ability to generalize across different datasets.

The model under discussion does not utilize recurrence or convolution. To effectively handle sequence data, it is essential to incorporate knowledge about the order of sequence elements. To achieve this, “positional encodings” are added at the foundational layers of both the encoder and decoder stacks. These encodings match the dimension, d_{model} , of the input embeddings, which allows for their summation. The literature mentions the option between fixed and learnable positional encodings [BSF94].

In the architecture, sinusoidal functions with varying frequencies are employed:

$$PE_{\text{pos}_{2i}} = \sin\left(\frac{\text{pos}}{10000^{2i/d_{\text{model}}}}\right)$$

$$PE_{\text{pos}_{2i+1}} = \cos\left(\frac{\text{pos}}{10000^{2i/d_{\text{model}}}}\right)$$

Here, pos denotes the position within the sequence, and i represents the respective dimension. Each dimension of the positional encoding corresponds to a sinusoidal wave. The frequencies of these sinusoids change in a geometric progression from 2π to 20000π . This method was selected based on the hypothesis that it would facilitate the model’s ability to learn attention based on relative positions, since for any constant offset k , the encoding $PE_{\text{pos}+k}$ can be linearly expressed in terms of PE_{pos} .

2.3 Summarization

Summarization is a challenge in NLP where the goal is to shorten a long document into a brief, clear summary that captures all important details from the original text. This task can be tackled in two main ways: extractive or abstractive summarization. In extractive summarization, specific parts of the original text—like tokens or full sentences—are selected and pieced together to create a summary. While these summaries are usually accurate, they can sometimes be choppy and lack smooth flow. On the other hand, abstractive summarization creates new text that wasn’t in the original document. This method allows for more versatile applications and smoother summaries, but it might include some hallucinations.

2.3.1 Datasets

A majority of extensive abstractive summarization datasets are primarily in English. These datasets have been systematically compiled through the process of web crawling from various sources. For instance, the XSUM dataset, developed by [NCL18], comprises approximately 227,000 news articles sourced from the BBC between 2010 and 2017, spanning a broad array of subjects. The primary aim of this dataset is to generate concise, single-sentence summaries. However, the unique methodology involves selecting the article’s first sentence as the summary. Another notable dataset is CNN/DailyMail, introduced by [NZG⁺16], which includes 93,000 articles from CNN in 2015 and 220,000 articles from DailyMail in 2017. The goal here is to produce bullet-point summaries, although the exclusion of article titles from these summaries occasionally results in the omission of critical contextual information. These summaries are intended to be read in conjunction with their

Figure 2.5: Number of Samples in Summarization datasets Over Time

respective titles. Among English-language datasets, CNN/DailyMail is frequently utilized in academic research.

Additionally, the Reddit TIFU dataset, curated by [KKK18], contains 120,000 posts from the TIFU (“Today I F*cked Up”) subreddit within the online platform REDDIT, gathered from the years 2013 to 2018. The summaries for these posts are derived from the TLDR (Too Long Didn’t Read) sections, typically authored by the original poster to provide a succinct overview of the content. The stringent guidelines of the TIFU subreddit help ensure a baseline level of reliability for these summaries. Unlike other datasets, Reddit TIFU offers a less formal approach to summarization.

In a multilingual context, MLSUM and XLSUM represent significant advancements in abstractive summarization datasets. Developed by [SDL⁺20], MLSUM includes 1.5 million entries from national news outlets across French, German, Spanish, Russian, and Turkish languages. Conversely, XLSUM, crafted by [HBI⁺21], comprises one million entries from various national BBC websites, encompassing over 44 languages. The quality of XLSUM has been verified through human evaluation. Complementing these, [MNBM20] introduced an additional dataset based on XSUM, which consists of human-annotated summaries that assess both factuality and faithfulness.

2.3.2 Models

The initial work in summarization introduced statistical [BMW00, WVDBK12] and compression [CL08, FA13] methods. However, it was the advent of fully data-driven, neural-network-based methodologies [RCW15], particularly inspired by advancements in Machine Translation with seq2seq models featuring RNN-based architectures and cross-attention [BCB16], that breathed new life into abstractive summarization.

Currently, abstractive summarization is widely employed to evaluate state-of-the-art pretrained Large Language Models (LLMs) and their ability to learn new tasks. This is typically done through either fine-tuning [RSR⁺20, LLG⁺19] or zero-shot learning [CND⁺23]. Fine-tuned LLMs like T5 [RSR⁺20] and BART [LLG⁺19] train with a seq2seq objective, where the summary is predicted based on the given source text. However, challenges persist, such as hallucination [DWV22] and memorization [XD21].

Memorization, commonly arising during training on large datasets with redundant text spans, can be mitigated through thorough data cleaning, particularly by removing duplicates [LIN⁺21]. Hallucination, with its numerous causes [MNBM20], can be addressed by using carefully curated, high-quality content-summary pairs and external knowledge bases [DWV22].

Extractive techniques have also been used to enhance generation and reduce hallucination. Pre-selecting content before summarization, as done by [SLM17], [SNN⁺20] and [GDR18], ensures that key information is not distorted. Some models, like [SOW⁺20], employ reinforcement learning for summarization with human feedback, while [SNN⁺20] and [HKM⁺20] advocate for controlled summarization using keywords or descriptive prompts.

For autoregressive models, decoding strategies such as greedy or beam search significantly affect the quality of the generated summaries [WMC22]. Multiple studies focus on aligning generation strategies with consistency. SummaReRanker [RJC22] optimizes for selecting the best summary from several generated options. Alternatives like PINOCCHIO [KSS⁺22] and BRIO [LLRN22] critique maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) and suggest post-processing summaries, with PINOCCHIO adjusting beam search using heuristics for model confidence.

Another research direction involves designing specific training tasks for summarization. PEGASUS [ZZSL20] employed Gap Sentence Generation (GSG) to pretrain on abstractive summarization tasks. FactPEGASUS [WB22] addresses factuality issues by incorporating more summarization-specific tasks, utilizing pseudo-summaries, and complementary self-supervised fine-tuning tasks.

In the field of multilingual abstractive summarization, research is limited. XLSUM's

fine-tuned mT5 [HBI⁺21, XCR⁺20] stands out as the only published and available multilingual model. While MLSUM’s paper [SDL⁺20] describes fine-tuning an M-BERT model, detailed procedures remain unavailable and the model isn’t openly accessible.

2.3.3 Evaluation

Evaluating the quality of natural language generation (NLG) models presents significant challenges due to the numerous criteria that must be considered, including fluency, coherence, factuality, adequacy, style, and grammar. In the context of summarization, models also need to generate concise summaries of the input document’s key points. The most commonly used evaluation metric for this purpose is the ROUGE score, which measures N-gram overlaps between generated and reference summaries [Lin04]. However, due to its reliance on the chosen tokenizer and its focus on vocabulary overlap, the ROUGE score has faced criticism from summarization practitioners [SLPS19, WCL20, HBUA⁺21, KKA⁺20].

Recent advancements in contextual similarity measures, which utilize large language models (LLMs), have improved evaluation precision and alignment with human preferences. Tools such as BLEURT [SDP20], LASE [HBUA⁺21], and BERT-score [ZKW⁺19] are increasingly used. BLEURT, for instance, updated its initial model in 2021 to include support for more than 100 languages, enhancing its accuracy and multilingual capabilities. NUBIA [KKA⁺20] aggregates embeddings from various models and calibrates them to predict a generation quality score.

Specific measures, such as SummaQA [SLPS19] and QAGS [WCL20], aim to assess factuality, coherence, and faithfulness. SummaQA, a BERT-based metric, evaluates Question Answering (QA) between the input text and generated summary without requiring a reference summary. QAGS also uses QA but assesses both the source content and generated summary, expecting similar results. Both metrics have shown better Spearman correlations with human evaluations. QuestEval [SDG⁺21] aims to unify precision and recall-based QA metrics by evaluating the content and generated summary against one another.

Despite these advances, some studies still find competitive results for the ROUGE score regarding its correlation with human judgment [SLPS19, WCL20]. ROUGE remains popular due to its speed, competitive performance, and simplicity. However, the newer metrics face challenges in adoption due to their relative slowness, biases associated with LLMs used for QA generation or evaluation, and later emergence compared to ROUGE.

Ngram Based Metrics

N-gram-based metrics, traditionally defined as a sequence of N consecutive words, have evolved to encompass sequences of N consecutive tokens due to the limitations of entire-word usage [Tel00]. For instance, the bigrams (2-grams) of the token sequence [“The”, “red”, “car”] would be (“The”, “red”) and (“red”, “car”). This technique effectively generates a new vocabulary derived from the original, which can be applied to assess keyword overlap using models like Bag of Words (BoW) and tf-idf. Although initially developed for language modeling, N-grams have also found utility in NLP evaluation as tools for assessing keyword overlap. When comparing two texts, such as a reference summary and a generated summary, or the original text and its summary, N-grams provide a basic heuristic for assessing textual similarity via vocabulary overlap, a computationally efficient approach.

The most commonly used N-gram-based metrics are BLEU [CBOK06], METEOR [BL05], and ROUGE [Lin04]. While BLEU and METEOR are primarily utilized for machine translation tasks, ROUGE is extensively applied in summarization research. The ROUGE metric suite includes N-gram-based measures like ROUGE-N, which evaluates co-occurrence statistics between reference and candidate summaries, and ROUGE-L, which assesses the longest common subsequence.

ROUGE-N quantifies the overlap between reference and candidate summaries. However, simply counting overlapping N-grams is insufficient due to variability in summary lengths. Instead, ROUGE-N precision, recall, and F_1 scores are calculated. The ROUGE-N recall is $\frac{c}{r}$, precision is $\frac{c}{g}$, and F_1 score is

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \cdot \text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{recall} + \text{precision}}$$

where c denotes overlapping N-grams, r is the reference N-grams count, and g represents the candidate N-grams count.

While N-gram-based metrics demonstrate some correlation with human preferences, caution is warranted, as they disregard sentence structure and semantic similarity.

Chapter 3

Dataset Creation

As outlined in the introductory section, Meltwater aggregates data from various web sources. These sources primarily consist of blogs and news articles, which often feature an “ingress”—a brief summary intended to encapsulate the essence of the corresponding web page. Typically, both the content and the ingress are extracted from HTML elements. Although Meltwater’s data pipeline initially processes the extracted text, numerous artifacts remain, including snippets of Java code, empty contents or summaries, and excessive whitespace. This section will discuss all the extra steps performed on top of the cleaning Meltwater already does on documents.

The initial 5TB dataset that has been gathered had close to 900 million documents across more than 110 languages, collected over the span of one year from May 2022 to May 2023. Each document comprised the web page’s content, the potential ingress, and associated metadata such as the URL, the detected language of the content, and the media type of the web page.

The data processing methodologies discussed herein are underpinned by two primary justifications: a text-quality rationale and a task-specific rationale. The text-quality rationale is largely independent of specific tasks, rooted in the objective to refine the dataset by removing irrelevant textual artifacts. Conversely, the task-specific rationale pertains directly to the requirements of abstractive summarization. For instance, decisions to exclude overly long or short summaries were made to ensure a consistent length distribution, reflecting a deliberate choice to tailor the summaries to a predefined criterion.

The process of cleaning and filtering the dataset was both extensive and meticulous, as detailed earlier. This endeavor not only refined the dataset but also unveiled promising research opportunities in the area of language-agnostic near-deduplication. As discussed in the Introduction, such rigorous preprocessing is essential for developing a high-quality model. The final dataset, which has been named MELTSUM, comprises approximately 25

million samples across 54 languages.

3.1 Technical Framework

Processing so much data, necessitates computational approaches beyond the capabilities of a single local machine if timeliness is a consideration. Therefore, large-scale datasets like this require the deployment of distributed computing tools.

One exemplary tool that facilitates this is Apache Spark [apab], which was employed using the Amazon Elastic Map Reduce service [awsc]. Apache Spark, a robust framework designed for large-scale data processing, facilitates the distribution of data across the nodes of a cluster, allowing localized operations to be conducted on each node before the results are consolidated as required. The coding for this deployment was done using Scala.

Moreover, the presence of near-duplicates within the dataset required a strategic adjustment. The complexity involved in developing necessary functionalities using Scala [sca] in conjunction with Spark led to the integration of Python [pyt] to address these specific challenges.

Selecting an appropriate data format is crucial and varied across different stages of the project. Initially, the dataset was formatted into multiple JSONL files. For enhanced efficiency in subsequent phases, the data storage format was switched to Apache Arrow [apaa], utilizing the 'datasets' library [huga] from HuggingFace [hugb]. This format is particularly well-suited for fine-tuning large language models (LLMs) on expansive datasets, facilitating more streamlined processing and analysis.

For two tasks, pre-existing services from Meltwater were employed: specifically, for the purposes of language detection and LSH (Locality-Sensitive Hashing).

3.2 General Crawling Issues

In addition to the standard text processing techniques typically employed in natural language processing, the challenges encountered in developing a dataset for abstractive summarization from web-crawled sources are twofold.

1. The generated summaries lack qualitative integrity. The most apparent manifestation of this problem occurs when the summary bears no relevance to the corresponding text, such as summaries consisting solely of metadata pertaining to the time and location of the article. More nuanced instances include summaries that fail to encapsulate the primary content of the text or erroneously introduce content not present in the original document.

2. The summaries exhibit excessive extractiveness. Although the sentences extracted might accurately reflect the content of the text, this characteristic is not inherently desirable within the context of the model’s objectives, particularly when the selected sentences are arbitrarily chosen from the text.

3.3 Initial Cleaning

The tokenizer strategy adopted for this research was specifically tailored to accommodate the linguistic characteristics of the dataset’s diverse languages. For languages that lack explicit word separators—such as Japanese, Chinese, Korean, Thai, Lao, Khmer, Javanese, and Tibetan—a per-character tokenizer was employed. Conversely, for languages where words are typically delimited by spaces, a space-based tokenizer was utilized. This approach ensured that the text processing was appropriately aligned with the orthographic conventions of each included language.

The initial processing of the dataset involved a series of straightforward operations aimed at enhancing the quality and uniformity of the data:

1. **Content and Summary Filtration:** Entries that were either empty or concluded with an ellipsis were removed, as an ellipsis typically indicates incomplete content.
2. **Whitespace Normalization:** All forms of white-spaces and similar characters, with the exception of new lines, were standardized to single white spaces, and any consecutive white spaces were eliminated.
3. **Anonymization of URLs and Emails:** URLs and email addresses within the text were replaced with [URL] and [MAIL] tokens, respectively.
4. **Code Snippet Removal:** JavaScript code snippets, delineated by `/**/` markers, were excised from both contents and summaries.
5. **Redundancy Reduction in Summaries:** Samples where the summary precisely replicated the start of the content, following normalization (removal of punctuation and white spaces and conversion to lowercase), were excluded.
6. **Elimination of Duplicate Content:** Exact duplicates of content were identified, and only one instance of each was retained.
7. **Token-Based Filtering:** The dataset was further refined based on the number of tokens:

- Exclusion of samples where the summary or the content was excessively brief.
- Removal of samples where the summary exceeded the content in length.
- Discarding samples where the summary was significantly shorter than the content (less than 0.005%).

8. **Language Concordance Check:** Samples were filtered out if the language of the content did not match the language of the summary.

The implementation of these basic operations culminated in a refined dataset comprising 43.7 million samples. Although this intermediary dataset represented a significant improvement over the initial collection, it still exhibited several persistent challenges. Addressing these issues is complex; however, it is feasible to develop heuristic solutions based on metrics derived from N-Gram analyses. The following delineates the problems identified and the heuristics applied.

Firstly, certain web contents, such as marketing articles, often repeated the same information with minor modifications. To ascertain a minimal level of content quality, articles exhibiting excessive redundancy were excluded. This was quantified by calculating the ratio of unique tokens to total tokens; samples where this ratio fell below a conservative threshold of 0.5—indicating that more than half of the words were repetitive—were removed from the dataset.

Secondly, efforts were made to eliminate summaries that were excessively similar to sentences within the content. This was assessed using two conservative criteria: the absolute number of common N-Grams and the ratio of common N-Grams to the total number of N-Grams in the summary, effectively measuring recall. A threshold was set such that both measures needed to be low for a sample to be retained, with N set arbitrarily at 17 to ensure stringent filtering. This focus on recall aimed to exclude summaries lacking in novel sentences.

Lastly, summaries that shared minimal lexical content with their corresponding articles were also filtered out. The criterion here was to maintain summaries that contained at least a basic level of lexical overlap with the content, reflecting an interest in summaries that incorporated key words, tokens, or concepts from the main text.

Metrics Used:

The final operations applied to refine the dataset, though seemingly arbitrary, are grounded in metrics commonly employed to assess the intrinsic quality of summaries ([HBI⁺21]; [NCL18]). Specifically, these metrics were adapted to measure both redundancy and novelty within the dataset as follows:

1. **Content Redundancy Metric:** The redundancy was calculated using the formula $\text{redundancy} = \frac{|\text{set}(S)|}{|S|}$, where S represents the N-Grams of the summary. Although originally applied to summaries ([HBI⁺21]), this metric was repurposed to assess content quality, premised on the notion that high redundancy in vocabulary indicates poor quality.
2. **N-Gram Recall Metric:** This metric, defined as $\text{NGramRecall} = \frac{|\text{set}(S) \cap \text{set}(C)|}{|\text{set}(S)|}$, was utilized, though it has not been found in academic literature. It served as a measure to evaluate the overlap between the N-Grams of the summary (S) and the content (C).
3. **Novelty Ratio Metric:** The novelty ratio, calculated as $\text{noveltyRatio} = 1 - \frac{|\text{set}(S) \cap \text{set}(C)|}{|\text{set}(C)|}$ ([NCL18]; [HBI⁺21]), was used to identify summaries that were excessively novel compared to their corresponding content.

Following these measures, the dataset was reduced to 44 million samples spanning 111 languages. Languages represented by fewer than 2,000 samples were subsequently excluded, resulting in a final count of 54 languages. This systematic curation aimed to enhance the dataset’s relevance and usability for further linguistic and computational analyses.

3.4 Eliminating Duplicates

Evaluating the quality of a dataset presents numerous challenges. Traditional metrics serve as useful heuristics but are flawed in that they overlook structural and semantic similarities. Furthermore, aggregating these metrics by language results in a loss of valuable detail. Although qualitatively assessing a sample set can be effective, this method is labor-intensive, prolonged, and inherently incomplete, especially when the dataset spans 110 languages. It is important to note that these methods rely on a horizontal evaluation approach—assessing at the level of individual samples—which is ill-suited for vertical analysis. Such an approach may overlook critical biases in the dataset, including frequent text spans or thematic biases.

In practical terms, fine-tuning a model on the initially created MELTSUM dataset revealed significant language-specific inconsistencies within the initial findings. Notably, poor ROUGE scores were observed for this model when assessed using the Arabic, Russian, and Chinese test sets from XL-SUM. Conversely, the performance of XL-SUM on these languages in MELTSUM did not align with those on other languages, suggesting issues with the quality of the reference summaries.

Further qualitative analysis of the predictions highlighted a pronounced tendency towards memorizing irrelevant summaries. Memorization is a significant problem for large

language models, often trained on extensive web-sourced datasets, which tend to include repetitive content. [LIN⁺21] suggest mitigating this by removing nearly identical text spans through precise duplication filters, which has been shown to reduce memorization and yield more reliable models. This issue of memorization extends to downstream tasks such as abstractive summarization, where [XD21] identified prevalent bigrams within datasets like XSUM and CNN/DM, indicative of broader repetitive text patterns.

Given the significant presence of duplicates associated with low-quality summaries in the created dataset, it was logical to explore the implementation of near-duplicate filtering strategies.

MinHash, a technique devised for swiftly estimating the similarity between two sets, coupled with Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH), which facilitates approximate nearest neighbor searches, enables the rapid and reliable detection of near-duplicates through an approximation of Jaccard similarity. MinHash employs numerous minwise hash functions that map integers to hash values through permutations, identifying the minimum hash value observed; this process allows for the efficient hashing of documents in linear time while conserving memory [Bro00]. [Bro00] demonstrated that the ratio of hash collisions to the total number of hash values provides an unbiased estimate of Jaccard similarity.

The Jaccard similarity index quantifies the similarity between two finite sets by dividing the size of their intersection by their union. However, this metric may not be suitable if the sets greatly differ in size, in which case metrics such as Jaccard set containment may offer a better alternative [ZNP16]. Given that the document summaries under consideration are of comparable lengths, the MinHash LSH approach is deemed appropriate [Bro00, GAK20, LRU20].

Although calculating the similarity between every pair of documents post-hashing is computationally quadratic relative to the number of documents, using LSH can streamline this process. By designing the hash buckets to group similar documents more likely than dissimilar ones, LSH efficiently approximates these calculations in feasible time [LRU20, Bro00]. The overall complexity of this method is $O(N \log N)$, where N is the total number of documents, rendering it an efficient strategy for detecting near-duplicates across such a vast number of documents.

Practical implementation of MinHash using the datasketch Python library involves calculating the minHash for each tokenized document and adding it to an LSH index. Subsequent querying for similar documents within the index eliminates the need for redundant computations for documents already identified as near-duplicates. Despite a set LSH threshold of 0.8, testing across multiple languages including English, Swahili, Thai, Italian, Russian, Korean and Hungarian yielded satisfactory deduplication results, with

Language	Duplicates
English	Published on 21/06/2022 at 15:51 ... Published on 03/02/2023 at 10:22 ...
Italian	Segui la sezione Arte per non perdere nessun nuovo post. Segui la sezione Salute per non perdere nessun nuovo post.
Hungarian	Mai hőmérséklet: 18C, páratartalom: 50%, ... Mai hőmérséklet: 23C, páratartalom: 56%, ...

Table 3.1: Example duplicates found using LSH and Jaccard similarity

many bucketed document pairs exhibiting Jaccard similarities even below the threshold (Table 3.1). This process facilitated the creation of the next version of the MELTSUM dataset, which comprises 25 million samples.

3.5 Automatic Pattern Clustering

At this point, many issues have been addressed, but still some remain. Training a model and looking at the summaries it produces on could see that one ongoing issue is memorization, which was mentioned earlier. Often, problems occur when there are repetitive phrases at the beginning of the text. Spotting these repetitions in large amounts of data is difficult. Therefore, a method was needed to identify these issues automatically, so manually checking all the data is not needed.

The occurrences of memorizations are attributed to the repeated emergence of identical patterns, leading to the model’s overfitting on these specific patterns. To address this issue, it is imperative to create a method for identifying these clusters of data. Observations from the summaries generated by the model, which was trained on the dataset developed in the preceding subsection, indicate frequent instances of hallucinated elements at the beginning of the summary and occasional presence of JavaScript code towards the end. These phenomena are illustrated in Table 3.2.

3.5.1 Pattern Tokenization

To effectively cluster textual patterns, a systematic approach begins with an essential step of tokenization. In this initial phase, all alphabetic characters within the text are replaced with the symbol “T” for text, while numeric characters are substituted with “N” for numbers. This basic tokenization process significantly reduces the text’s complexity by transforming intricate words and numbers into simplified, uniform tokens, thus facilitating

“/home/news releases/” prefix	home / news releases / Revelation Biosciences Inc. Announces ...
	home / news releases / Bacco Farms Announces 420 Holiday ...
	home / news releases / IAR Launches IAR Embedded Secure IP ...
“/PRNewswire/ block in the beginning”	CAMBRIDGE, Mass., April 12, 2023 /PRNewswire/ – Leap Therapeutics, Inc. (Nasdaq:LPTX) today announced ...
	PITTSBURGH, April 12, 2023 /PRNewswire/ – Viatriis Inc. (NASDAQ: VTRS) plans to report ...
	NEW YORK, April 12, 2023 /PRNewswire/ – Professor Edward Altman, one of ...
Javascript at the end	For the latest news and updates, follow us on Google News. <code>/**/ window.yaContextCb.push(=>{ Ya.Context.AdvManager.render({ renderTo: 'yandex_rtb_R-A-639714-10',})})</code>
	F7B46FF6F7AD/Grit+A+Weight+Maintenance+Tool <code>/**/ window.yaContextCb.push(=>{ Ya.Context.AdvManager.render({ renderTo: 'yandex_rtb_R-A-639714-10',</code>
	EXCLUSIVE: Childhood Obesity Can Lead To Heart Attack In Kids- Expert Shares All About Fostering Healthy Habits <code>/**/ window.yaContextCb.push(=>{ Ya.Context.AdvManager.render({ renderTo: 'yandex_rtb_R-A-639714-10',</code>

Table 3.2: Junk examples in the predictions

easier pattern recognition.

Following this substitution, the method progresses by consolidating consecutive identical tokens into a single token to further compact the data. For instance, a series of “TTT”, which might arise from a sequence of letters such as ‘ABC’, is combined into a single “T”. Similarly, a sequence like “NNN” originating from a string of numbers such as ‘123’, is collapsed into a single “N”. This step is crucial as it minimizes the granularity of the data, emphasizing the general pattern of alphanumeric presence over the specifics of the individual characters or numbers. For example, the text “AAA111BBB222” initially transitions to “TTTNNNTTTNNN” and is ultimately reduced to “TNTN” markedly simplifying the pattern recognition process.

Additionally, this tokenization approach includes a categorization for non-alphanumeric characters, which are typically found interspersed between letters and numbers—such as spaces, tabs, commas, and periods. These characters are grouped with their adjacent tokens to preserve meaningful patterns without introducing extraneous noise into the tokenized data. Notably, characters like periods, which are frequently used in date formats (e.g., “2023.01.01”), are incorporated into the grouping rules to ensure these are recognized as cohesive numeric tokens (“N”) rather than fragmented by punctuation. This strategy is crucial for maintaining the clarity and semantic integrity of numerical data within the text, particularly for dates and decimal values, which could be misinterpreted if tokenized separately.

Furthermore, it is imperative to maintain other special characters as delimiters in the tokenized patterns. This is illustrated by the segment “/PRNewswire/”, which is aptly tokenized as “/T/”, ensuring that such markers are preserved to demarcate distinct segments within the text accurately.

An additional operational consideration is the computational burden posed by applying this tokenization method across extensive text. Processing the entire text can generate a vast number of results, subsequently making the grouping phase highly resource-intensive. To circumvent this issue, the procedure concentrates on the initial 100 characters of each text segment. This targeted approach allows for the efficient extraction of patterns without the exhaustive computational demand that would arise from broader application. This methodological refinement ensures both efficiency and effectiveness in pattern extraction from large textual datasets.

Ingress tokenization steps:

1. Take the first 100 characters of the ingress.
2. Group all consecutive alphabetic characters together into a text token “T”.

3. Group all consecutive numeric characters together into a number token “N”.
4. Merge all the “extra characters” (spaces, tabs, commas, periods) around text tokens into the text token.
5. Merge all the “extra characters” (spaces, tabs, commas, periods) around number tokens into the number token.
6. Merge all the consecutive text tokens into one.
7. Merge all the consecutive number tokens into one.

3.5.2 Pattern Clustering

Following the initial tokenization of the text at the start of the documents to identify patterns, further refinement is implemented through additional filtering steps. Initially, all text tokens are removed, and any adjacent numeric tokens are consolidated. This consolidation ensures that, in the absence of text tokens, the resulting pattern is at least two characters in length. This criterion is crucial for confirming that the pattern includes not only text and numbers but also incorporates at least one special character, thereby addressing scenarios where an ingress simply contains some numbers without any extraneous elements.

Subsequently, the documents are clustered based on three specific attributes: the content language, the host (which is derived from the document’s source URL), and the extracted pattern of the ingress. To enhance the relevance and systematic integrity of the results, the data is then filtered to include only those occurrences that appear at least ten times. This threshold helps eliminate isolated anomalies that could otherwise inflate the result set disproportionately.

For analytical purposes, five illustrative examples are selected for each distinct pattern identified. These examples facilitate a detailed examination of the ingress patterns and are documented in Table 3.3. This table provides insights into the patterns extracted using distributed computing methods, which were instrumental in managing the extensive data involved. The use of distributed computing was particularly vital for maintaining all data groups within memory, thereby significantly accelerating the clustering and filtering processes.

Ultimately, the clustering yielded 371,515 entries, corresponding to 74,303 unique patterns when considering five samples for each pattern. Given the considerable volume, manual examination of all patterns is impracticable. An initial simplification involved refining the frequency threshold to 1,000 occurrences, since the model does not overfit based on

Figure 3.1: Clustering entries distribution by language

minimal exposure to recurring patterns in a dataset approaching 25 million samples. Further refinement was achieved by excluding quotation marks from the extracted ingress patterns, as these are typically unhelpful in delineating meaningful patterns.

Implementing these two criteria in the distributed pattern recognition process effectively reduced the number of entries to 2,255, or 451 distinct patterns. This quantity remains substantial but is manageable for manual review to determine the validity of each identified pattern. Figure 3.1 illustrates the number of entries extracted per language, the majority of entries were recognized in the zh-Hans language group.

Upon thorough review, 114 patterns were classified as valid and necessitated cleaning, whereas 337 were dismissed as inaccuracies. The patterns identified effect close to half a million ingresses in total.

3.5.3 Pattern Conversion

The main goal of this text clustering process is to methodically remove unnecessary elements from the text by using identified patterns. To do this, it's crucial to transform these patterns into regular expressions that programming languages can use to effectively filter out unwanted parts. However, this task is not simple. A significant challenge is that multiple variations of the same pattern can appear in the text, caused by the variability in the data that follows the pattern.

In this approach, the focus is on the first 100 characters of the text to identify patterns.

Extracted Pattern	Ingress
NTN-N:NT	13 DE Diciembre 2022 - 01:04 El herido se encuentra en un estado ...
	27 DE Marzo 2023 - 01:01 El padre de la víctima manifestó su preocupación por lo que pueda ...
	15 DE Mayo 2022 - 01:01 El progenitor de la víctima de tres años redujo al ...
T(T) -T	TEHRAN (Tasnim) – California is burning. Wildfires are tearing ...
	TEHRAN (Tasnim) – According to an agreement signed in Ashgabat ...
	TEHRAN (Tasnim) – Tens of thousands of people were being evacuated to emergency ...
/T/T	/PŘEHLED STATISTICKÝCH ZAJÍMAVOSTÍ Z KRAJE/ Lenka Trojková z Brna ...
	/FOTOGALERIE/ V Muzeu Českého krasu byla ...
	/KANONÝR DENÍKU/ Nebyl sice tím nejgólovějším borcem ...
NT-T	24.08.2022 Dani Olmo ist am Dienstag beim Fußball-Bundesligisten ...
	07.06.2022 Nach dem schlechten Abschneiden der SPD bei der Landtagswahl ...
	05.08.2022 Mit dem Verkauf konventionell aufgezogener Tiere als Bio-Schweine ...

Table 3.3: Extracted pattern examples

This method helps to limit the number of different patterns by focusing on a consistent part of the text. While having multiple patterns isn't necessarily a problem and could be handled through several redundant filtering steps, the main issue is that these patterns often include more than just the unnecessary parts.

Converting the extracted patterns automatically into regex patterns for the above reason is not trivial and could only be possibly done with complex techniques. The development of such techniques is not that beneficial though as the number of patterns is not so many and could be processed by hand. So this was the chosen way to proceed forward.

When performing text analysis, the process of identifying and transforming text patterns into regular expressions (regex) involves dealing with both simple and complex patterns. This transformation is crucial because it allows programming languages to effectively remove unnecessary parts of text, improving the clarity and usefulness of the data.

1. **Simple Patterns:** Simple patterns are those that have a clear and repetitive structure, making them easy to spot and convert into regex expressions. For example, news articles might consistently start with a location and date stamp, or a specific formatting style like "TEHRAN (Tasnim) –". The regex pattern for this would be straightforward and directly matches the structure using regex syntax, such as `^TEHRAN \ (Tasnim\ ) –`, which accurately targets the beginning of these text entries. These patterns are easy to handle because of their predictability. Table 3.4
2. **Complex Patterns:** On the other hand, complex patterns include variations and might require a more detailed approach to convert them into regex. These patterns could mix different types of data such as names, dates, and descriptions within a single pattern. For example, entries that contain different data points like city names, dates, and agency codes in various configurations need a more intricate regex. A pattern like `TNT(T).-T` might be turned into a regex like `^(\pL+ ?)+, \p{N}+ \p{L}+ \ (EFE\)\.-`, which uses placeholders for letters and numbers, ensuring it can handle different text inputs flexibly. Table 3.5
3. **Utilizing Simplified Regex** In some cases, it might be more efficient to use a simplified regex pattern that does not strictly align with the extracted text pattern. For instance, if there is JavaScript code at the end of a text segment marked by `/**/`, it may be practical to filter out everything following this marker, regardless of the preceding text structure. This approach involves creating a regex such as `//.*` which efficiently removes any text following the `/**/` pattern. This method can be particularly useful when the aim is to clean up text entries from unwanted coding

snippets or extraneous data appended at the end of the content, simplifying the data cleaning process.

By converting these extracted text patterns into regex, automated systems are enabled to detect and discard unnecessary or irrelevant text parts, making data processing smoother and enhancing the utility of textual data in automated systems. The choice to handle some patterns manually, due to their manageable size or complexity, represents a practical balance between using automation for efficiency and maintaining human oversight for accuracy.

As the final step these created patterns have been used to clean the dataset. The number of samples did not change in this step as only part of the text were removed.

3.6 Control Codes

After completing the previous cleaning steps and training another model, it was noticed that the generated summaries occasionally still included some unwanted elements at the start. This indicates that there might be some remaining issues with the data cleaning process or the model itself.

The authors of the CTRLSUM paper [HKM⁺20] have developed a novel framework for controllable text summarization. This framework allows users to influence various features of the summaries generated by providing keywords or descriptive prompts. The CTRLsum model can adapt to different summarization controls without needing extra annotations or predefined control aspects during training. The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated across three domains and five specific summarization controls, including entity-centric, length-controllable, and question-guided summarization. Additionally, CTRLsum also performs well in standard summarization tasks, achieving top results on the CNN/DailyMail dataset.

To solve the problem of unwanted content in the summaries, the technique mentioned earlier has been adjusted to better suit this particular need. This adjustment aims to improve the cleaning of the summaries, ensuring that the final outputs are of higher quality enhancing the overall usefulness of the summaries.

From the previous data cleaning phase, where data patterns were clustered and subsequently sanitized using custom-developed regex patterns, it is now possible to identify which entries have been effectively cleaned. This identification is important as it allows for the strategic enhancement of the training dataset through the targeted use of control codes. To optimize the quality and reliability of the training data, a comprehensive strategy has been formulated, delineated as follows:

Extracted Pattern	Regex Pattern	Ingress
T(T) -T	^TEHRAN \ (Tasnim\) -	TEHRAN (Tasnim) – The reports of bombardment of a maternity facility in Donetsk raise concern, Spokesman for the UN Secretary-General Stephane Dujarric said Monday, adding that this is an apparent violation of international humanitarian law.
		TEHRAN (Tasnim) – Iranian Foreign Minister Hossein Amirabdollahian expressed the country’s readiness to broaden the political, economic and trade relations with Jordan.
		TEHRAN (Tasnim) – A US federal judge said Saturday she’s inclined to grant Donald Trump’s request to bring in an outsider to oversee the review of more than two dozen boxes of materials the FBI seized from the former president’s Florida estate earlier this month.
T»T»T	^Home » \p{L}+ »	Home » Entertainment » Wu Qili broke the truth about Zhuolin wandering on the streets and bombarding the new hug Andi, saying that she was sick and did nothing!
		Home » Tech » IMAGICA EEX Conducts Demo of Really Sensible Are living Welding Employing Vertical Pictures and Front-end Transfer Screens – PRONEWS : Digital Video Production Website Magazine
		Home » World » I thought I was holding out due to high oil prices, but Russia’s third quarter GDP fell 4%

Table 3.4: Simpler patterns converted to regex

Extracted Pattern	Regex Pattern	Ingress
TNT(T).-T	$\text{^\{\\pL+ ?\}+, \\p\{N\}+ \\p\{L\}+ \\(EFE\\)\.}$	<p>Redacción deportes, 15 ene (EFE).- El reencuentro con el gol del sueco Alexander Isak fue providencial, con un valor de tres puntos para su equipo, el Newcastle, otra vez atascado ante el Fulham (1-0) y que enderezó su rumbo en la Premier gracias al tanto del exjugador de la Real</p> <p>Jerusalén, 25 ene (EFE).- Israel y Estados Unidos llevan a cabo estos días un ejercicio militar conjunto de gran envergadura en territorio israelí. Es el de mayores dimensiones que ambos países han realizado, y se interpreta como un mensaje ante Irán y otros adversarios de estos</p> <p>Nicosia, 31 ago (EFE).- El Gobierno de Chipre anunció este miércoles la decisión del Consejo de ministros de establecer por primera vez en la historia del país un salario mínimo nacional, que se decidió fijar en 940 euros al mes.</p>

Table 3.5: Complex pattern converted to regex

1. In scenarios where a data sample has not been flagged as containing junk text, its purity cannot be conclusively determined. The mere absence of detected contaminants does not fully guarantee their absence. In such cases, no specific control code is assigned, acknowledging the potential oversight in junk detection.
2. Upon identification of a pattern that suggests the presence of undesirable content within the text, a dual approach is adopted to address the findings:
 - (a) For the unaltered version of the text, which retains the original content including any detected impurities, an [UNCLEAN] control code is prefixed to the content. This label serves as a clear indicator that the ingress may still contain elements that are non-essential or disruptive.
 - (b) For the version of the text that has been cleaned, removing all recognized extraneous elements, a [CLEAN] control code is added at the beginning. This notation confirms the successful removal of unwanted content.

This methodical approach does not increase the precision of the data cleaning process but it significantly improves the integrity and effectiveness of the data used for training purposes. By clearly distinguishing between cleaned and uncleaned texts, the training processes can be better tailored to achieve more accurate and reliable outcomes.

Chapter 4

Experiments

Tackling the challenges of fine-tuning with a vast multilingual dataset involves several complexities. Given a dataset of 25 million samples, careful planning is essential regarding the framework, model size, learning strategies, and hardware to achieve effective learning within a reasonable timeframe and budget. The multilingual nature of the dataset, with languages of different sizes, adds another layer of difficulty. The pre-trained model must learn multiple languages while retaining its previous knowledge and avoiding a disproportionate focus on high-resource languages.

In this chapter, the choice of model (specifically mT5) will be discussed, exploring its unique features, and describing the different experiments conducted.

4.1 Technical Framework

The utilization of Amazon SageMaker [awsd] for training deep learning models is justified by several critical factors. First, it abstracts the intricacies of managing and configuring the infrastructure required for deep learning, offering a fully managed service that oversees compute provisioning, Jupyter notebook management, and training orchestration. Second, it offers flexible model development by supporting widely-used deep learning frameworks such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Apache MXNet, as well as providing pre-built algorithms and the flexibility to incorporate custom code. Finally, SageMaker delivers scalable training by adjusting compute resources dynamically to accommodate extensive workloads, eliminating the need for manual infrastructure oversight. In essence, Amazon SageMaker furnishes a comprehensive and adaptable platform for deep learning model training, enabling machine learning practitioners to concentrate on model development instead of infrastructure management.

Data parallelism [KSH12], a highly utilized methodology, enhances the training of neu-

ral networks by distributing datasets across several processors. Each processor independently computes gradient updates, which are subsequently aggregated. The versatility of this technique is derived from its ability to function independently of the neural network’s architecture, making it adaptable to any model with an objective function that can be decomposed into a sum over individual training examples. On the other hand, model parallelism [DCM⁺12], which allocates parameters and computational workloads across processors for the same training examples, is inherently restricted by the model’s architecture and size. In deep neural networks, training typically encompasses three primary phases: a forward pass to compute the loss, a backward pass to determine gradients, and an optimization step to adjust parameters. Data parallelism seamlessly integrates into this workflow by generating multiple replicas of the model, each handling a distinct subset of data through the forward and backward passes. These replicas then synchronize gradients or updated parameters depending on the chosen algorithm, allowing neural network training to effectively scale across numerous processors, thereby significantly enhancing computational efficiency. These are the reasons this technique has been used during training the models.

4.2 Architecture Design

The mT5 model, presented by [XCR⁺20], stands out as the singular pre-trained model that satisfies the specified criteria for multilingual text processing. Its distinguishing features include:

1. **Language Agnosticism:** The model is engineered to be inherently language-independent, negating the necessity of predefining the input language, which is pivotal for truly multilingual applications.
2. **Extensive Multilingual Pre-training:** It has been pre-trained on a dataset spanning 101 languages, leveraging an oversampling smoothing strategy to enhance the representation of low-resource languages. This pre-training also encompasses the 54 languages from the created dataset, further highlighting its expansive linguistic coverage.
3. **Accidental Translation Prevention:** The model is specifically trained to avoid unintended translation effects, thereby ensuring that the generated output maintains consistency with the input language.
4. **Comparative Applicability:** In the XLSUM paper [HBI⁺21], mT5’s utility in multilingual tasks was validated.

Building on the foundational design of T5.1.1, which itself is a derivative of T5 [RSR⁺20], mT5 adopts a sequence-to-sequence (seq2seq) architecture. Its training regimen employed a span-corruption objective, alongside a suite of optimization strategies and architectural refinements, such as substituting the traditional ReLU activation function with GEGLU. The XLSUM study utilized the mT5-base variant, which encompasses approximately 580 million parameters. Future research directions suggest evaluating the performance trajectory of larger models within the mT5 family, with parameters ranging from 1.2 billion to 13 billion.

Furthermore, the tokenizer used in mT5 was pre-trained on the mC4 dataset [XCR⁺20], ensuring intrinsic compatibility with the multilingual nature of the model’s training corpus, thus eliminating the need for additional modifications.

While there are a variety of open-source large language models (LLMs) available online, such as T5, BART, BERT, RoBERTa, GLM, XLM, PEGASUS, and GPT-2, the vast majority have been trained predominantly on English datasets, making them less ideal for multilingual tasks. To date, only five LLMs have been specifically designed for multilingual usage: mBERT, XLM-R, NLLB, MBart, and mT5. Despite the renown of mBERT [DCLT18] and XLM-R [CKG⁺19] as multilingual models, they lack the seq2seq architecture required for this task, as they operate as autoencoders. Similarly, while NLLB [CjCÇ⁺22] and MBart [LGG⁺20] are seq2seq models optimized for machine translation, their need to explicitly define input and output languages limits their applicability in this context.

4.3 Sampling Strategies

To construct a multilingual dataset, one must first establish the joining strategy. Following the approach of XLSUM, which was influenced by [LC19], this dataset consists of pairs of content summaries sampled based on a multinomial distribution across the language samples. This approach ensures that content and summary pairs are representative of a diverse array of languages while accounting for the differences in resources available for each language.

Given n languages, a smoothing factor $\alpha \in [0, 1[$, and f_i representing the frequency of the i -th language (i.e., $\frac{n_i}{\sum_j n_j}$), the probabilities $\{q_i\}_i$ are determined by:

$$q_i = \frac{f_i^\alpha}{\sum_j f_j^\alpha}$$

These probabilities are integral to the sampling method, which aims to address the imbalance in language resources. The approach uses α to control the emphasis on language frequencies, allowing for flexible adjustment in the prominence of low-resource languages.

The aim of this sampling method is to ensure that languages with fewer resources are sampled more frequently than if selection was solely based on frequency (i.e., $\alpha = 1$). The process of constructing a multilingual dataset follows a simple procedure: a language is drawn according to $\{q_i\}_i$, then a sample is taken from that language. This ensures that each language is proportionately represented according to its adjusted frequency.

Two distinct sampling strategies can be applied here. With limited samples in low-resource languages, a decision must be made about when to cease sampling. An under-sampling strategy involves stopping once any language’s samples are exhausted, while an oversampling strategy means sampling continues until all samples from every language have been utilized at least once. These strategies have implications for how data is handled, especially for languages with limited resources.

Due to significant language frequency imbalances, the undersampling approach may lead to underutilization of high-resource languages. Conversely, oversampling can cause low-resource language samples to appear multiple times during training, risking overfitting. It is noteworthy that the XLSUM project employed the oversampling method for its training which is the sampling that will be using in this project as well. By allowing low-resource languages to appear multiple times, oversampling ensures these languages have enough data representation, albeit with a higher risk of overfitting.

These approaches highlight the challenges in creating multilingual datasets that aim for balanced representation while dealing with resource constraints. The selection of the sampling strategy profoundly impacts the quality and representativeness of the dataset, directly influencing the performance of multilingual models. This intricate balance makes multilingual dataset construction a complex yet critical task.

4.4 Training

In total 3 models have been trained with 3 different dataset configurations. All three trainings ran on the whole datasets that have been given to them. With all the trainings using the full potential of the dataset was the goal.

The first two training jobs were performed on ml.p3.16xlarge [awsa] instances that had 8 V100 Tesla GPUs. Then to make the training faster and cheaper a migration has been performed to use the ml.p4d.24xlarge [awsb] instance with 8 A100 GPUs. With the latest-generation NVIDIA A100 Tensor Core GPUs, each P4d instance delivers on average 2.5x better DL performance compared to previous-generation P3 instances and also P4d instances deliver up to 60% lower cost to train ML models compared to P3 instances. All parameters of the instances used can be seen in Table 4.1.

Instance type	Instance count	vCPUs	Instance Memory (GB)	GPUs	GPU Memory (GB)	GPU Peer to Peer	EBS Bandwidth (Gbps)
ml.p3.16xlarge	1	64	488	8x Tesla V100	128	NVLink	14
ml.p4d.24xlarge	1	96	1152	8x A100	320	600 GB/s NVSwitch	19

Table 4.1: Training instances used

The dataset was partitioned into train, validation, and test subsets, utilizing a 90/10/10% division, respectively. For languages with datasets exceeding 200,000 samples, the testing and validation subsets were capped at 20,000 samples each. On the contrary for languages with datasets smaller than 4,000 samples, these subsets were restricted to 400 samples each.

The dataset has been pretokenized before running the training to save a lot on the training time. The dataset has been tokenized in a way that the maximum input source length was 512 and the maximum target length was 84 tokens. This is also how the model has been set up for the training. There were many parameters that had to be chosen to get a good model during the training. For all of the model training jobs all parameters have been the same. Once the parameters have been carefully chosen they have been used for all three training jobs. Oversampling was used with a smoothing factor of 0.8. For reproducibility a random seed was created and then set for all the training jobs. The per device train batch size was set to 4 in the case of p3 instance runs and 10 when running the training on the p4 instance.

The learning rate, set to $1e-4$, establishes the step size for weight updates, ensuring a gradual and stable convergence. This is further refined by the cosine learning rate scheduler [LH16], which adjusts the learning rate in a cosine shape, facilitating faster learning initially and then gradually tapering off to fine-tune the model. The warmup steps [GDG⁺17], numbering 10,300, provide a gentle increase in the learning rate at the onset of training, which helps in stabilizing the gradient updates and reducing noise, particularly in large models. The accumulation of gradients across eight steps before a backward pass mimics larger batch sizes, thereby optimizing memory use and computational efficiency [HSM17]. The weight decay [KH91] parameter of 0.01 introduces a regularization effect, constraining

the growth of weights to prevent overfitting and ensuring better generalization. Label smoothing [SVI⁺16, MKH19], with a factor of 0.1, mitigates overconfidence by softening the one-hot labels, leading to improved model robustness. Finally, the Adafactor optimizer [SS18] optimizes weight updates with enhanced memory efficiency and adaptive learning rates, a feature particularly advantageous for large-scale natural language processing tasks. Collectively, these parameters synergistically aim to achieve a balanced training process that is both resource-efficient and capable of producing a model with strong generalization capabilities.

Each training iteration was conducted for a single epoch, primarily due to the significant time and financial resources required. Initially, the training tasks executed on p3 instances spanned approximately five days. However, a strategic transition to high-performance optimized instances resulted in a notable reduction in training duration, curtailing the process to a mere two days.

Parameter	Value (Original)	Value (Optimized)
instance_type	ml.p3.16xlarge	ml.p4d.24xlarge
max_source_length	512	512
max_target_length	84	84
smoothing_factor	0.8	0.8
oversample_multilingual	true	true
per_device_train_batch_size	10	40
learning_rate	1e-4	1e-4
lr_scheduler_type	cosine	cosine
warmup_steps	10300	10300
gradient_accumulation_steps	8	8
weight_decay	0.01	0.01
label_smoothing_factor	0.1	0.1
optim	adafactor	adafactor

Table 4.2: Model Configuration Parameters Comparison

Chapter 5

Results

This comparative analysis studies three proprietary summarization models—designated as v1, v2, and v3—and the XLSUM model, serving as a comparative benchmark. The evaluation spans a diverse linguistic spectrum utilizing both ROUGE metrics for quantitative analysis and manual qualitative assessments to gauge the integrity of the summaries. Findings underscore the incremental improvements achieved through sophisticated data processing techniques, highlighting their pivotal role in reducing fabricated content and elevating the quality of summaries.

5.1 Evaluation Methods

The burgeoning volume of textual data necessitates advanced automated summarization tools to facilitate efficient information digestion. The performance of these models is critically dependent on the caliber of the training data and the methodologies applied during their development. This paper evaluates three iterations of a bespoke summarization model, each reflecting progressive advancements in data cleaning and processing techniques. By comparing these models against the XLSUM benchmark, the study aims to delineate their efficacy across various languages and outline best practices for summarization training.

- **Model Training:**

- **v1:** Employs elementary data cleaning methods to eliminate rudimentary noise from the training corpus.
- **v2:** Enhances the initial model by rigorously purging residual non-essential content from the training dataset, known to degrade training quality and model output.

- **v3:** Introduces sophisticated control codes to distinctly identify cleaned versus uncleaned text segments, providing targeted guidance to the model during training.
- **Evaluation Metrics:**
 - **Quantitative:** Utilization of ROUGE metrics—specifically ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L F-scores—to assess summarization efficacy.
 - **Qualitative:** Beyond ROUGE scores, exhaustive manual evaluations are conducted to ascertain the coherence, relevance, and absence of fictitious content in the summaries.
- **Test Set:** The models are appraised using a multilingual dataset initially compiled for the v2 model evaluation, ensuring a consistent assessment framework.

5.2 Evaluation Results

- **Quantitative Evaluation:**
 - Analysis reveals that although the v1 and v2 models display superior ROUGE scores relative to v3, suggesting robust initial performance, these metrics do not fully reflect the enhanced cleanliness of summaries noted in v3.
 - Notably, the XLSUM model demonstrates commendable performance in processing Chinese texts, possibly indicative of specialized training or dataset-specific advantages.
 - Discrepancies such as the anomalously high ROUGE scores in Thai language evaluations for the XLSUM model call for further scrutiny into potential methodological or dataset biases.
- **Qualitative Evaluation:**
 - Qualitative reviews indicate a marked reduction in hallucinated content from v1 to v2, with v3 further minimizing inaccuracies and irrelevant inclusions through the use of control codes. These qualitative enhancements, though not mirrored in ROUGE scores, accentuate the efficacy of the iterative enhancement strategy in improving data quality and summary accuracy.

The divergence between quantitative and qualitative evaluation outcomes accentuates the need for multifaceted assessment techniques in the development of summarization models. While ROUGE scores serve as a preliminary metric of summary effectiveness, they often

Language	Score type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
ar	rouge1-F	0.3614	0.3702	0.3618	0.3607	0.1469
ar	rouge2-F	0.1978	0.2099	0.1958	0.1924	0.0500
ar	rougeL-F	0.3039	0.3156	0.3098	0.3020	0.1204
en	rouge1-F	0.3418	0.3491	0.3373	0.3417	0.1469
en	rouge2-F	0.1451	0.1537	0.1510	0.1499	0.0498
en	rougeL-F	0.2664	0.2693	0.2581	0.2666	0.1202
es	rouge1-F	0.3694	0.3609	0.3472	0.3544	0.1479
es	rouge2-F	0.1400	0.1338	0.1299	0.1283	0.0502
es	rougeL-F	0.2627	0.2575	0.2585	0.2674	0.1211
hi	rouge1-F	0.3569	0.3578	0.3444	0.3498	0.1460
hi	rouge2-F	0.1502	0.1556	0.1396	0.1449	0.0496
hi	rougeL-F	0.2697	0.2704	0.2567	0.2617	0.1198
ru	rouge1-F	0.2861	0.2858	0.2594	0.2615	0.1495
ru	rouge2-F	0.1034	0.1059	0.0942	0.0970	0.0508
ru	rougeL-F	0.2053	0.2058	0.1955	0.1951	0.1223
zh-Hans	rouge1-F	0.3997	0.4064	0.3980	0.4006	0.4140
zh-Hans	rouge2-F	0.2295	0.2335	0.2149	0.2208	0.2009
zh-Hans	rougeL-F	0.3572	0.3609	0.3554	0.3605	0.3201

Table 5.1: Rouge score examples where v3_no_cc stands for the model trained on the 3rd version of the dataset without using control codes during inference and v3_cc stands for the same with using control codes during inference.

overlook subtle yet critical enhancements that significantly enhance user satisfaction and utility. The findings emphasize the essential role of advanced data cleaning and strategic control code implementation in crafting models that generate superior summaries. Additionally, the variation in performance across languages underscores the necessity for further model tuning and linguistic adaptation.

5.3 Evaluation Conclusion

This exhaustive examination highlights the significance of integrating both quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods to develop more proficient summarization models. Future directions will focus on refining control code integration, enhancing adaptability to diverse linguistic contexts, and addressing performance evaluation anomalies, propelling the field

of automated text summarization forward. This research provides a foundation for future advancements in model training and establishes a benchmark for the thorough assessment of summarization technologies.

Chapter 6

Future work

6.1 Further Analysis of Results

Despite the thorough assessments detailed in previous sections, certain observations—especially the score differences across languages like Thai, Arabic, and Russian—call for more detailed examination. The unusually high performance of the XLSUM model in these languages suggests there might be biases in the methodology or specific issues with the datasets. To confirm the reliability of the findings and potentially improve the models further, additional analyses are necessary.

A deeper statistical analysis is essential, focusing on examining the distribution and consistency of ROUGE scores across different languages, particularly Thai, Arabic, and Russian. This will help pinpoint any unusual patterns or trends that could have impacted the results. Also, reevaluating the methods used in compiling the datasets and conducting the tests for these languages might reveal important insights.

Moreover, by comparing the results for these languages with others within the same model framework, any language or cultural factors can better understood that might be influencing the discrepancies in performance. A thorough qualitative review, especially of the summaries produced in Thai, Arabic, and Russian, could provide deeper insights into the nature of the content generated by the models.

The main goal of this further analysis is to ensure the accuracy and fairness of the model evaluations across all languages, thereby enhancing the reliability and usefulness of the models globally. Such efforts will also help refine the models to handle language nuances more effectively, thus improving their utility worldwide. If these issues are addressed, it might strengthen the trustworthiness and effectiveness of automated summarization tools in multilingual settings.

6.2 Maximizing Models Potential

The finetuning of mT5-base was performed as a demonstrative exploration into the efficacy of the MELTSUM dataset for multilingual abstractive summarization. It suggests that modest modifications could substantially enhance the quality of the summaries generated. Primarily, the imposed maximum length for input tokens, set at 512, and the summary length capped at 84, were primarily determined by computational and temporal limitations. This restriction reduces the maximum batch size supported during training and extends the processing time for each sample. Crucially, limiting input length may truncate essential context, potentially omitting critical information, making it imperative to evaluate the model’s performance with extended input lengths. Additionally, the efficacy of mT5 models appears intrinsically linked to their scale [XCR⁺20]; with a notable performance disparity observed in natural language generation tasks between the mT5-base, which comprises 580 million parameters, and the mT5-large, which encompasses 1.2 billion parameters. Thus, transitioning to a model with a larger parameter count could precipitate a significant escalation in performance.

6.3 Inference Speed Improvements

Due to the auto-regressive nature of the inference process in sequence-to-sequence (seq2seq) models, the inference batch size is typically limited to one. Running the trained mT5 models it can quickly be seen from benchmarks that its speed does not meet the operational requirements of Meltwater’s production environment. Several strategies may be employed to enhance inference speed.

Pruning, described by [Jan89], entails the removal of some neural network parameters while attempting to retain model performance.

Knowledge distillation, as outlined by [HVD15], involves transferring the knowledge from a larger model (the teacher) to a smaller one (the student). Various methods of distillation exist, as described by [GYMT21], with the most direct approach involving the simultaneous processing of data through both the teacher and student models, and the student model learning through the back-propagation of a distillation loss.

Quantization involves storing model weights in formats requiring less precision than the typical 32-bit floating-point format, such as bf16, fp16, or int8, as discussed by [BMS⁺19]. While quantization primarily reduces memory footprint, the resultant increase in available memory can facilitate the use of larger batch sizes, thereby enhancing inference speed.

Faster decoding techniques are also proposed in the literature, such as the aggressive

decoding technique by [GXS⁺22], which suggests decoding initially in a non-auto-regressive manner followed by a rapid verification using an auto-regressive process.

[GIR⁺24] explores a novel training approach for large language models like GPT [WHL⁺23] and Llama [TLI⁺23], where the models are trained to predict multiple future tokens simultaneously, rather than just the next token. The authors introduced a method that utilizes multiple independent output heads to predict a sequence of future tokens from a common model structure. This multi-token prediction approach enhances sample efficiency and improves performance on various tasks, including coding and natural language processing, without increasing training time. They found that larger models and prolonged training periods particularly benefit from this method. Specifically, models using this approach significantly outperformed traditional single-token prediction models on coding benchmarks. Additionally, models trained to predict four tokens at a time were three times faster during inference, showing both improved efficiency and capability.

6.4 Dataset Bias

The MELTSUM dataset was systematically collected from the web over a one-year period, from May 2022 to May 2023. As a result, it intrinsically focuses on topics and significant events that occurred during this specific timeframe. Notable instances include Russia’s invasion of Ukraine and the launch of ChatGPT by OpenAI, which are repeatedly mentioned across the dataset. This temporal focus provides a rich, contemporary snapshot of global events and technological advancements that are highly relevant for current research and applications.

However, the dataset’s comprehensive scope does bring certain challenges. Although Meltwater’s web crawlers are designed to filter and mitigate the inclusion of sensitive content, the vast nature of data collection across diverse sources means that some sensitive content may inadvertently be included. The presence of such content necessitates the implementation of rigorous precautions. Researchers and developers using the MELTSUM dataset for training machine learning models must be attentive. They should employ robust filtering techniques to further minimize the risk of utilizing sensitive or inappropriate data, ensuring that the models developed are ethical and contextually aware. This careful approach is essential to harness the dataset’s potential responsibly while avoiding the perpetuation of biases or harmful content.

6.5 Model Bias

mT5, a model originally pretrained on mC4, leverages a vast and unrefined dataset extracted from the public Common Crawl web scrape. This dataset, characterized by its substantial volume and diversity, unfortunately received minimal to no curation during its compilation. As a consequence, it is replete with duplicate entries, which could potentially lead to memorization issues within the mT5 model. Such memorization issues are of particular concern as they might compromise the model’s ability to generalize from its training data to real-world applications effectively.

Furthermore, the MELTSUM dataset, which is used to finetune mT5, exhibits its own set of challenges, notably a pronounced subject bias. This bias is a result of the dataset’s composition, which disproportionately represents certain themes and topics that were prevalent during the data collection period. Models finetuned on such a dataset are at risk of inheriting and perpetuating these biases. This skewed knowledge acquisition could manifest in biased outputs when the model is deployed in diverse real-world scenarios.

The interaction between the initial extensive but uncurated training on mC4 and subsequent finetuning on a biased dataset like MELTSUM necessitates a strategic approach to model training. It is essential for developers to implement advanced data processing and model training techniques that address these issues. Techniques such as data deduplication, bias mitigation strategies, and robust validation processes are critical.

6.6 Augmenting Hallucination Data

The dataset designated for summarization contained a large number of entries, many of which included unnecessary or irrelevant text, commonly referred to as ‘junk text’. These entries were carefully identified and removed to prepare for training models that use control codes. The use of control codes significantly improves the models’ ability to clean the data, ensuring that only high-quality information is produced.

To further enhance the model’s ability to identify and remove junk text, it could be useful to deliberately create more data that includes such unwanted content. By marking this newly created data as [UNCLEAN], the model is provided with additional examples of what to exclude. This method is likely to improve the model’s accuracy in distinguishing between useful and non-useful content.

Additionally, to generate this data with junk text more efficiently, advanced language models such as ChatGPT [WHL⁺23], Gemini [TAB⁺23] etc. might be considered to be used. These models have the processing power and linguistic capabilities to produce a

variety of text inputs that a system might encounter, including junk text. Utilizing these models can speed up the process of data generation, allowing for quicker improvements to the training models. This approach ensures that the models are well-equipped to handle and process real-world data more effectively.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

This research presented a pioneering multilingual abstractive summarization dataset, characterized by its unprecedented scale (25 million samples) and extensive linguistic diversity covering 54 languages. Initially, the thesis provided a comprehensive introduction to essential concepts within the architecture of Large Language Models (LLMs) and the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP), highlighting the evolution from traditional tokenization techniques to advanced trainable tokenizers like Byte-Pair Encoding, and from early neural network models to the sophisticated Transformer architecture. This was augmented by a discussion on the significant impacts of sequence-to-sequence models, attention mechanisms, and pre-trained language models such as BERT and GPT-3, which have fundamentally transformed NLP tasks through their innovative pre-training and fine-tuning capabilities.

In detailing the methodology for dataset curation, the paper outlined the rigorous processes involved in compiling and refining an initial collection of over 900 million documents across more than 110 languages. This extensive corpus was meticulously cleaned and filtered using advanced heuristic techniques like MinHash and Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH), combined with distributed computing tools like Apache Spark, to produce a high-quality subset named MELTSUM. This subset not only included 25 million samples in 54 languages but also integrated unique control codes to distinguish between cleaned and potentially impure text, enhancing the dataset's utility for training robust summarization models.

The validation of the dataset involved a detailed fine-tuning process using the state-of-the-art mT5 model—a sequence-to-sequence multilingual Large Language Model. The training leveraged scalable cloud infrastructures such as Amazon SageMaker, employing data parallelism and advanced computing resources to handle the large-scale data efficiently. The fine-tuning process was optimized through strategic sampling strategies and

parameter adjustments, ensuring a balanced representation of both high-resource and low-resource languages.

A thorough evaluation of the model was then conducted, comparing it against three proprietary models and the XLSUM benchmark through both quantitative metrics and qualitative analysis. The results highlighted incremental improvements in summarization quality, demonstrating the effectiveness of the advanced data cleaning methods and the sophisticated training techniques employed. The findings not only confirmed the high performance of the newly developed models but also emphasized the need for ongoing enhancements in control code integration and linguistic adaptability.

In conclusion, while this research has laid a substantial foundation for advancing the capabilities of multilingual summarization, it also opens several avenues for further refinement. The discussion of future work, including the exploration of larger model sizes, advanced inference techniques, and mitigation of biases in dataset and model, underscores the vast potential for continued advancements in the field. Through iterative improvements and extended research initiatives, there remains a significant opportunity to advance multilingual NLP technologies, enhancing their accuracy, efficiency, and fairness in real-world applications.

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Appendix A

Dataset Sizes

Dataset sizes with the size of the datasplits. Also comparing the total size to the one in XLSUM.

Language code	MELTSUM Total	Train	Validation	Test	Language name	XLSUM Total
es	4284399	4244399	20000	20000	Spanish	47636
zh-Hans	2280536	2240536	20000	20000	Chinese (Simplified)	46702
en	1990812	1950812	20000	20000	English	329592
ko	1880500	1840500	20000	20000	Korean	5507
de	1791721	1751721	20000	20000	German	0
tr	1290501	1250501	20000	20000	Turkish	33970
it	1218550	1178550	20000	20000	Italian	0
pl	1107136	1067136	20000	20000	Polish	0
vi	966882	926882	20000	20000	Vietnamese	40137
pt	873002	833002	20000	20000	Portuguese	71752
fr	864266	824266	20000	20000	French	10869
ru	687261	647261	20000	20000	Russian	77803
nl	487481	447481	20000	20000	Dutch	0
ja	429538	389538	20000	20000	Japanese	8891
ro	419165	379165	20000	20000	Romanian	0
el	402367	362367	20000	20000	Greek	0
fa	344559	304559	20000	20000	Persian	59063

Table A.1: Dataset sizes by language

APPENDIX A. DATASET SIZES

Language code	MELTSUM Total	Train	Validation	Test	Language name	XLSUM Total
hi	329030	289030	20000	20000	Hindi	88472
id	307634	267634	20000	20000	Indonesian	47802
hu	296130	256130	20000	20000	Hungarian	0
zh-Hant	270846	230846	20000	20000	Chinese (Traditional)	46713
cs	262205	222205	20000	20000	Czech	0
he	238354	198354	20000	20000	Hebrew	0
hr	175637	140509	17564	17564	Croatian	0
da	167003	133603	16700	16700	Danish	0
ar	153868	123094	15387	15387	Arabic	46897
sv	151719	121375	15172	15172	Swedish	0
uk	143851	115081	14385	14385	Ukrainian	53999
ca	118506	94804	11851	11851	Catalan	0
sk	90591	72473	9059	9059	Slovak	0
no	88016	70412	8802	8802	Norwegian	0
sl	86717	69373	8672	8672	Slovenian	0
te	85377	68301	8538	8538	Telugu	13025
sr	84523	67619	8452	8452	Serbian	18187
lt	78485	62789	7848	7848	Lithuanian	0
lv	52807	42245	5281	5281	Latvian	0

Table A.2: Dataset sizes by language

APPENDIX A. DATASET SIZES

Language code	MELTSUM Total	Train	Validation	Test	Language name	XLSUM Total
fi	41763	33411	4176	4176	Finnish	0
bn	40733	32587	4073	4073	Bengali	10126
bg	40295	32235	4030	4030	Bulgarian	0
gu	39454	31564	3945	3945	Gujarati	11397
mk	29440	23552	2944	2944	Macedonian	0
kn	28972	23178	2897	2897	Kannada	0
et	18397	14717	1840	1840	Estonian	0
sq	18149	14519	1815	1815	Albanian	0
is	15768	12614	1577	1577	Icelandic	0
ta	13579	10863	1358	1358	Tamil	20276
th	9520	7616	952	952	Thai	8268
sw	6713	5371	671	671	Swahili	9872
be	4417	3533	442	442	Belarusian	0
ms	4399	3519	440	440	Malay	0
ml	2540	1740	400	400	Malayalam	0
af	2413	1613	400	400	Afrikaans	0
kk	1690	890	400	400	Kazakh	0
cy	1688	888	400	400	Welsh	12164

Table A.3: Dataset sizes by language

Appendix B

Summarization Evaluation Results

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
af	rouge1-F	0.2870	0.2957	0.2735	0.2752	0.1458
af	rouge2-F	0.0700	0.0766	0.0649	0.0712	0.0496
af	rougeL-F	0.2052	0.2132	0.2051	0.2035	0.1197
ar	rouge1-F	0.3614	0.3702	0.3618	0.3607	0.1469
ar	rouge2-F	0.1978	0.2099	0.1958	0.1924	0.0500
ar	rougeL-F	0.3039	0.3156	0.3098	0.3020	0.1204
be	rouge1-F	0.1706	0.1742	0.1590	0.1622	0.1459
be	rouge2-F	0.0458	0.0488	0.0395	0.0421	0.0495
be	rougeL-F	0.1299	0.1340	0.1274	0.1315	0.1196
bg	rouge1-F	0.2511	0.2529	0.2138	0.2160	0.1457
bg	rouge2-F	0.0647	0.0651	0.0477	0.0486	0.0496
bg	rougeL-F	0.1730	0.1721	0.1591	0.1572	0.1197
bn	rouge1-F	0.2125	0.2064	0.1781	0.1774	0.1457
bn	rouge2-F	0.0808	0.0811	0.0585	0.0630	0.0495
bn	rougeL-F	0.1658	0.1681	0.1455	0.1462	0.1196
ca	rouge1-F	0.2974	0.3048	0.2972	0.2973	0.1458
ca	rouge2-F	0.1044	0.1131	0.1058	0.1054	0.0496
ca	rougeL-F	0.2240	0.2347	0.2265	0.2253	0.1196
cs	rouge1-F	0.1880	0.1835	0.1592	0.1586	0.1458
cs	rouge2-F	0.0502	0.0475	0.0367	0.0366	0.0494
cs	rougeL-F	0.1306	0.1281	0.1158	0.1155	0.1196

Table B.1: Rouge scores

APPENDIX B. SUMMARIZATION EVALUATION RESULTS

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
cy	rouge1-F	0.3275	0.3177	0.3445	0.3188	0.1458
cy	rouge2-F	0.1614	0.1525	0.1742	0.1535	0.0496
cy	rougeL-F	0.2615	0.2516	0.2838	0.2637	0.1197
da	rouge1-F	0.3120	0.3225	0.2999	0.2895	0.1470
da	rouge2-F	0.0996	0.1037	0.0855	0.0811	0.0498
da	rougeL-F	0.2115	0.2156	0.2052	0.2009	0.1205
de	rouge1-F	0.3199	0.3141	0.2948	0.2901	0.1468
de	rouge2-F	0.1258	0.1265	0.1151	0.1092	0.0497
de	rougeL-F	0.2280	0.2224	0.2204	0.2127	0.1201
el	rouge1-F	0.2961	0.2961	0.2773	0.2647	0.1457
el	rouge2-F	0.1222	0.1215	0.1159	0.0998	0.0495
el	rougeL-F	0.2135	0.2139	0.2108	0.1946	0.1195
en	rouge1-F	0.3418	0.3491	0.3373	0.3417	0.1469
en	rouge2-F	0.1451	0.1537	0.1510	0.1499	0.0498
en	rougeL-F	0.2664	0.2693	0.2581	0.2666	0.1202
es	rouge1-F	0.3694	0.3609	0.3472	0.3544	0.1479
es	rouge2-F	0.1400	0.1338	0.1299	0.1283	0.0502
es	rougeL-F	0.2627	0.2575	0.2585	0.2674	0.1211
et	rouge1-F	0.1707	0.1692	0.1555	0.1576	0.1457
et	rouge2-F	0.0462	0.0479	0.0376	0.0393	0.0495
et	rougeL-F	0.1346	0.1363	0.1244	0.1298	0.1196
fa	rouge1-F	0.3932	0.3831	0.3751	0.3724	0.1458
fa	rouge2-F	0.2008	0.1937	0.1863	0.1815	0.0494
fa	rougeL-F	0.3204	0.3139	0.3057	0.3075	0.1195
fi	rouge1-F	0.2116	0.2188	0.2030	0.1981	0.1474
fi	rouge2-F	0.0817	0.0837	0.0720	0.0718	0.0500
fi	rougeL-F	0.1703	0.1707	0.1683	0.1647	0.1208
fr	rouge1-F	0.3502	0.3509	0.3410	0.3497	0.1480
fr	rouge2-F	0.1531	0.1520	0.1532	0.1532	0.0501
fr	rougeL-F	0.2374	0.2387	0.2409	0.2433	0.1211
gu	rouge1-F	0.2051	0.1977	0.1880	0.1892	0.1457
gu	rouge2-F	0.1017	0.0941	0.0795	0.0806	0.0496
gu	rougeL-F	0.1754	0.1703	0.1638	0.1648	0.1196

Table B.2: Rouge scores

APPENDIX B. SUMMARIZATION EVALUATION RESULTS

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
he	rouge1-F	0.2530	0.2523	0.2498	0.2406	0.1458
he	rouge2-F	0.1266	0.1249	0.1258	0.1143	0.0494
he	rougeL-F	0.2047	0.2039	0.2087	0.1949	0.1196
hi	rouge1-F	0.3569	0.3578	0.3444	0.3498	0.1460
hi	rouge2-F	0.1502	0.1556	0.1396	0.1449	0.0496
hi	rougeL-F	0.2697	0.2704	0.2567	0.2617	0.1198
hr	rouge1-F	0.2204	0.2249	0.1935	0.1891	0.1457
hr	rouge2-F	0.0642	0.0628	0.0526	0.0491	0.0496
hr	rougeL-F	0.1676	0.1670	0.1558	0.1511	0.1196
hu	rouge1-F	0.2577	0.2564	0.2458	0.2431	0.1482
hu	rouge2-F	0.0883	0.0843	0.0740	0.0714	0.0502
hu	rougeL-F	0.1947	0.1939	0.1898	0.1873	0.1212
id	rouge1-F	0.3440	0.3421	0.3394	0.3383	0.1458
id	rouge2-F	0.1898	0.1866	0.1885	0.1866	0.0496
id	rougeL-F	0.2875	0.2846	0.2889	0.2883	0.1197
is	rouge1-F	0.2660	0.2602	0.2574	0.2533	0.1459
is	rouge2-F	0.0962	0.0965	0.0896	0.0846	0.0496
is	rougeL-F	0.2020	0.1989	0.1993	0.1954	0.1196
it	rouge1-F	0.2879	0.2972	0.3022	0.2900	0.1476
it	rouge2-F	0.1217	0.1272	0.1283	0.1197	0.0501
it	rougeL-F	0.2151	0.2238	0.2337	0.2249	0.1209
ja	rouge1-F	0.3974	0.3799	0.3540	0.3522	0.1460
ja	rouge2-F	0.2199	0.2041	0.1737	0.1701	0.0483
ja	rougeL-F	0.3260	0.3153	0.2895	0.2928	0.1197
kk	rouge1-F	0.2977	0.2947	0.2608	0.2591	0.1459
kk	rouge2-F	0.1859	0.1751	0.1586	0.1566	0.0496
kk	rougeL-F	0.2813	0.2725	0.2448	0.2427	0.1198
kn	rouge1-F	0.3401	0.3399	0.3462	0.3419	0.1458
kn	rouge2-F	0.1924	0.1908	0.1959	0.1942	0.0495
kn	rougeL-F	0.2989	0.2965	0.3079	0.3002	0.1196
ko	rouge1-F	0.1616	0.1524	0.1470	0.1437	0.1458
ko	rouge2-F	0.0685	0.0615	0.0519	0.0484	0.0496
ko	rougeL-F	0.1553	0.1423	0.1361	0.1326	0.1195

Table B.3: Rouge scores

APPENDIX B. SUMMARIZATION EVALUATION RESULTS

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
lt	rouge1-F	0.1910	0.1878	0.1789	0.1757	0.1457
lt	rouge2-F	0.0680	0.0652	0.0660	0.0605	0.0496
lt	rougeL-F	0.1554	0.1516	0.1502	0.1435	0.1196
lv	rouge1-F	0.2016	0.2000	0.1938	0.1930	0.1459
lv	rouge2-F	0.0668	0.0732	0.0682	0.0637	0.0496
lv	rougeL-F	0.1606	0.1598	0.1508	0.1482	0.1196
mk	rouge1-F	0.2829	0.2820	0.2644	0.2652	0.1458
mk	rouge2-F	0.0881	0.0818	0.0700	0.0782	0.0496
mk	rougeL-F	0.2040	0.2034	0.1944	0.1953	0.1196
ml	rouge1-F	0.2606	0.2672	0.2580	0.2580	0.1457
ml	rouge2-F	0.1328	0.1400	0.1355	0.1390	0.0495
ml	rougeL-F	0.2273	0.2328	0.2270	0.2259	0.1197
ms	rouge1-F	0.2405	0.2447	0.2339	0.2412	0.1458
ms	rouge2-F	0.0955	0.0961	0.0932	0.1006	0.0495
ms	rougeL-F	0.1881	0.1881	0.1844	0.1912	0.1196
nl	rouge1-F	0.3067	0.3130	0.2863	0.2863	0.1466
nl	rouge2-F	0.1001	0.1016	0.0855	0.0891	0.0498
nl	rougeL-F	0.2160	0.2177	0.2085	0.2099	0.1200
no	rouge1-F	0.2707	0.2669	0.2565	0.2568	0.1477
no	rouge2-F	0.0768	0.0757	0.0669	0.0715	0.0501
no	rougeL-F	0.1950	0.1924	0.1860	0.1894	0.1208
pl	rouge1-F	0.2484	0.2536	0.2422	0.2364	0.1457
pl	rouge2-F	0.1006	0.0997	0.0943	0.0934	0.0496
pl	rougeL-F	0.1854	0.1817	0.1883	0.1832	0.1196
pt	rouge1-F	0.3276	0.3238	0.3189	0.3184	0.1484
pt	rouge2-F	0.1431	0.1428	0.1310	0.1295	0.0502
pt	rougeL-F	0.2522	0.2480	0.2470	0.2493	0.1211
ro	rouge1-F	0.3170	0.3147	0.3020	0.2931	0.1476
ro	rouge2-F	0.1192	0.1155	0.1101	0.0998	0.0500
ro	rougeL-F	0.2372	0.2310	0.2227	0.2138	0.1208
ru	rouge1-F	0.2861	0.2858	0.2594	0.2615	0.1495
ru	rouge2-F	0.1034	0.1059	0.0942	0.0970	0.0508
ru	rougeL-F	0.2053	0.2058	0.1955	0.1951	0.1223

Table B.4: Rouge scores

APPENDIX B. SUMMARIZATION EVALUATION RESULTS

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
sk	rouge1-F	0.1841	0.1807	0.1891	0.1793	0.1459
sk	rouge2-F	0.0610	0.0593	0.0684	0.0636	0.0494
sk	rougeL-F	0.1520	0.1456	0.1532	0.1467	0.1197
sl	rouge1-F	0.2481	0.2483	0.2330	0.2293	0.1458
sl	rouge2-F	0.0896	0.0880	0.0748	0.0746	0.0496
sl	rougeL-F	0.1810	0.1822	0.1754	0.1691	0.1197
sq	rouge1-F	0.3217	0.3172	0.3200	0.3196	0.1458
sq	rouge2-F	0.1230	0.1196	0.1207	0.1223	0.0496
sq	rougeL-F	0.2600	0.2570	0.2553	0.2553	0.1196
sr	rouge1-F	0.2611	0.2551	0.2309	0.2373	0.1458
sr	rouge2-F	0.0897	0.0891	0.0714	0.0768	0.0495
sr	rougeL-F	0.2013	0.1976	0.1807	0.1821	0.1195
sv	rouge1-F	0.3148	0.3048	0.2984	0.2953	0.1475
sv	rouge2-F	0.1054	0.1038	0.0903	0.0885	0.0500
sv	rougeL-F	0.2122	0.2099	0.2069	0.2084	0.1208
sw	rouge1-F	0.3458	0.3426	0.3119	0.3092	0.1459
sw	rouge2-F	0.1344	0.1263	0.1042	0.1113	0.0495
sw	rougeL-F	0.2527	0.2464	0.2286	0.2296	0.1196
ta	rouge1-F	0.1920	0.2042	0.1753	0.1937	0.1459
ta	rouge2-F	0.1042	0.1156	0.0855	0.1054	0.0496
ta	rougeL-F	0.1828	0.1951	0.1641	0.1841	0.1197
te	rouge1-F	0.2608	0.2412	0.2356	0.2161	0.1458
te	rouge2-F	0.1453	0.1255	0.1260	0.1154	0.0496
te	rougeL-F	0.2266	0.2071	0.2030	0.1889	0.1196
th	rouge1-F	0.2583	0.2526	0.2467	0.2472	0.3755
th	rouge2-F	0.1015	0.1102	0.0846	0.0925	0.1317
th	rougeL-F	0.2393	0.2294	0.2238	0.2243	0.3428
tr	rouge1-F	0.3740	0.3585	0.3777	0.3772	0.1469
tr	rouge2-F	0.2199	0.2061	0.2292	0.2344	0.0498
tr	rougeL-F	0.3270	0.3120	0.3360	0.3372	0.1204
uk	rouge1-F	0.2347	0.2207	0.2268	0.2278	0.1458
uk	rouge2-F	0.0992	0.0888	0.0924	0.0960	0.0495
uk	rougeL-F	0.1923	0.1788	0.1849	0.1883	0.1196

Table B.5: Rouge scores

APPENDIX B. SUMMARIZATION EVALUATION RESULTS

Language code	Score Type	v1	v2	v3_no_cc	v3_cc	XLSUM
vi	rouge1-F	0.3214	0.3308	0.3111	0.3015	0.1457
vi	rouge2-F	0.1783	0.1869	0.1716	0.1637	0.0496
vi	rougeL-F	0.2520	0.2579	0.2467	0.2367	0.1197
zh-Hans	rouge1-F	0.3997	0.4064	0.3980	0.4006	0.4140
zh-Hans	rouge2-F	0.2295	0.2335	0.2149	0.2208	0.2009
zh-Hans	rougeL-F	0.3572	0.3609	0.3554	0.3605	0.3201
zh-Hant	rouge1-F	0.2992	0.2867	0.2802	0.2702	0.4141
zh-Hant	rouge2-F	0.1128	0.1152	0.1011	0.0987	0.2010
zh-Hant	rougeL-F	0.2395	0.2346	0.2321	0.2235	0.3202

Table B.6: Rouge scores

Appendix C

Example Summaries

C.1 English 1

Content

The body of cricket icon Shane Warne will finally be returned to Australia today as his former doctor lifts the lid on what caused his shock death in Thailand. A private jet carrying the 52-year-old sportsman is due to touch down in Melbourne's Tullamarine Airport on Thursday following a nine-hour flight. The final voyage comes after an autopsy earlier this week confirmed Warne had died of a suspected heart attack on the Island of Koh Samui last Friday. The body of Australian icon Shane Warne (pictured in 2019) will finally be returned to Australia today, almost a week after his shock death in Thailand. An ambulance carrying the cricketer moves from the Surat Thani Hospital to Suvarnabhumi International Airport after an autopsy confirmed he died of natural causes. A state funeral to pay tribute to the cricketer will be held on March 30 at the Melbourne Cricket Ground, with as many fans as possible allowed to attend. 'There will be no limits on crowds and that sort of stuff,' he said. 'It will be a very big event, it will be a celebration of his life as it should be.' Warne's close friends and family are expected to hold a private ceremony to farewell the sporting legend from as early as next week. It comes as his former doctor Dr. Peter Brukner breaks his silence on what he believes caused the 52-year-old's shock death, blaming the spin king's lifestyle. He told Perth radio hosts Basil Zempilas and Xavier Ellis that his death was hastened by a combination of a longstanding smoking habit, poor diet and other factors. 'Warne, if he had heart disease, which sounds like he did, you know, that didn't happen overnight in Thailand,' he said on Triple M Breakfast on Wednesday. 'It's been happening for 20, 30 years from smoking, poor diet, etc, etc.' A state funeral to pay tribute to the cricketer will be held on March 3 at the Melbourne Cricket Ground, (pictured) with as many fans as possible allowed to attend.

Target Ingress

Body of cricket legend Shane Warne, 52, to be returned to Australia on Thursday An autopsy earlier this week confirmed cricketer died of suspected heart attack State funeral to be held at the Melbourne Cricket Ground on March 30 Victorian Premier Daniel Andrews said as many as possible allowed to attend

MELTSUM Summary

A private jet carrying the 52-year-old sportsman is due to touch down in Melbourne's Tullamarine Airport on Thursday The final voyage comes after an autopsy earlier this week confirmed Warne had died of a suspected heart attack on the Island of Koh Samui last Friday.

XLSUM Summary

Australia's spin king has said he will celebrate his life as it should be.

C.2 English 2

Content

In the era of the COVID pandemic and amid the surging delta variant, virtual learning has become a staple for Arkansas students. But for students with poor Internet connection, virtual learning can be difficult if not impossible. Superintendents at Magazine and Paris said that the lack of Internet in their towns has been disruptive throughout their struggle with online learning. "We did everything that we could to try to mediate that," Paris Superintendent Wayne Fawcett said. At both schools, they put wifi hotspots throughout the community. In Paris, Fawcett said that he tried to put hotspots outside of town, so kids who live there did not have to drive all the way into the city for wifi. Magazine Superintendent Beth Shumate said that some students struggled to get to those community hotspots. "It becomes an equity issue very quickly," Shumate said. In Booneville, Superintendent Trent Goff said that the hotspots were sufficient for his students. After those were established on Booneville school campuses, Goff said it was a nonissue. This year's plan Not all schools will continue to offer virtual learning. At Magazine, the district is partnering with outside entities to provide about 15 kids with the opportunity to learn online. The program is already filled, meaning the rest of the students will have to learn in person. "What we found, and what most of our parents found, is that most of our students learned better face to face," Shumate said. Last year, her teachers taught both in-person and online classes. This year, no Magazine teachers will teach students virtually. Students who are forced to quarantine will either take home paper packets to complete their assignments or will complete their assignments through Google Classroom if they have Internet. Goff

said that Booneville will handle its online learning similarly to Magazine's program. The district will contract out its virtual learning program and a limited number of students will be allowed to learn virtually. Last year, Booneville teachers also managed both online and in-person classes. They will not do so this year. The Paris School Board will decide on Aug. 12 whether it will allow students to attend school online. Fawcett said the Paris School District was not going to offer virtual learning, but the surge in COVID cases has caused the district to reconsider its position. "I suspect we will," have a virtual option, Fawcett said. Fawcett is still trying to determine how virtual learning will work across different grade levels. "What it will look like at each building may be different," Fawcett said. Last year, teachers managed their own individual virtual classrooms. Fawcett said he is not sure if that is how the district will approach online learning for the upcoming school year. Internet connection In both Magazine and Booneville, companies are installing new fiber-based systems to upgrade the towns' wifi. Both towns received money to do the project from the Arkansas Rural Connect program, which is dispersing funds to areas that lack Internet throughout the state. Dobson Fiber, an Internet provider, is completing the wifi upgrade in Booneville. The provider applied for and received the grant through the Arkansas Rural Connect program. The money comes from the Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security Act, also known as the CARES Act, said John Zeiler, a corporate development manager with Dobson Fiber. The CARES Act is providing \$4.4 million to the project. The total cost of the project is approximately \$5.9 million. Dobson Fiber is paying for the additional \$1.5 million that the CARES Act is not covering. The company is putting in fiber to create Internet access from Greenwood to Booneville, building off of the small fiber system that is already in Greenwood. The system will reach people in Booneville who do not have access to the Internet. The areas are scattered throughout Booneville. The fiber system works by creating a physical line that contains pieces of glass. Pulses of light travel down the line to create the connection, Joseph Sanford, the director of digital health and innovation for the Institute for Digital Health and Innovation at the University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences, explained in a previous Times Record article. Zeiler said he hopes to be done with the project by the end of the year. The company is waiting for its building permits to be approved, and then it will begin construction. In Magazine, construction has already begun on its system. The state allotted the company \$1,025,692 to improve Magazine residents' access to the Internet. The state will cover 80 percent of the grant, and the Magazine Telephone Company will pay the other 20 percent, said Denny Stone, a representative of the company. The company is contracting Cowboy Splicing to splice the cable together to make the fiber.

Target Ingress

Communities throughout the state are trying local hotspots, limited virtual classrooms, Google Classroom, and private-public partnerships laying fiber in an effort to accommodate families with poor Internet connection.

MELTSUM Summary

The lack of Internet in both Arkansas schools has become a staple for students. But for students with poor Internet connection, virtual learning can be difficult if not impossible. In both Magazine and Booneville, companies are installing new fiber-based systems to upgrade the towns' wifi.

XLSUM Summary

Two schools in Arkansas have announced plans to allow students to learn virtually.

C.3 Hungarian 1

Content

Az orosz védelmi miniszter, Szergej Sojgu hadseregtábornok jelentette Putyinnak, a fegyveres erők legfőbb parancsnokának, hogy parancsának megfelelően a stratégiai rakétacsapatok, az Északi és a Csendes-óceáni Flotta, valamint a nagy hatótávolságú légi parancsnokság megerősített személyzettel megkezdték a harci szolgálat teljesítését“ - közölte a védelmi minisztérium hétfői közleményében. Putyin vasárnap kérte fel Sojigut és Valerij Geraszimov vezérkari főnököt, hogy az orosz fegyveres erők stratégiai elrettentő erejét ”különleges harci szolgálatra“ állítsák. Az elnök azután rendelte el a fokozott készségi fokozat bevezetését, hogy azt állította, ”vezető NATO-országok fő tisztségviselői“ ”agresszív kijelentéseket“ tettek az országával szemben, a Washington és szövetségesei által Moszkvára kirótt gazdasági szankciókon túl - írja az Interfax. Putyin nem pontosította, hogy kik, milyen megjegyzéseket tettek, de az Interfax szerint a bejelentés előtt néhány órával Liz Truss brit külügyminiszter azt mondta a Sky Newsnak adott interjújában, hogy ha Oroszország Ukrajnában zajló katonai műveletét nem ”állítják le“, a válság ”a NATO-val való konfliktusba torkollhat“. Az Ukrajnával kapcsolatos legfontosabb híreket ezen a linken olvashatja.

Target Ingress

Készenlétbe állt megerősített személyzettel az orosz nukleáris triász - azaz a nukleáris szárazföldi, légi és tengeri elrettentő erők, jelentette Szergej Sojgu védelmi miniszter Vlagyimir Putyin elnöknek - írja az Interfax.

MELTSUM Summary

Az orosz elnök vasárnap rendelte el a fokozott készségi fokozat bevezetését, hogy azt állította, ”vezető NATO-országok fő tisztségviselői“ ”agresszív kijelentéseket“ tettek az országával szemben.

XLSUM Summary

Ukrajna - a NATO-val - "agresif" byanatokat a Kremlin, a Kremlin és a Nato-k a k o nk ó n ó k olók , Ukrajn a harci s é r e t e k i l

C.4 Hungarian 2

Content

Tényleg annyira fontos a csere? Azt minden vezető tudja, hogy amikor huzamosan hét fok alá csökken a hőmérséklet, akkor a nyári gumi rideggé válik, és sokkal nagyobb az esélye a csúszásnak és a baleseteknek. Ugyanez elmondható a téli gumiról, csak itt éppen 7 fok feletti időről beszélhetünk. Ilyenkor az abroncs elkezd kopni, miközben a biztonságos közlekedésből is sokat veszít. Ez azt jelenti, hogy mindenki évente kétszer felkeresi a szervizet, és lecseréli az abroncsokat. Szinte mindenki! A négyévszakos gumi úgy lett kialakítva, hogy a futófelülete közelebb álljon a nyárihoz, azonban a vegyületét tekintve a kettő közé kerüljön. Innentől kezdve a hideg és meleg hónapok során is használható, tehát nem kell szervizbe rohanni a csere miatt, vagy legalábbis nem mindenkinek. Persze, mielőtt elrohannánk vásárolni egy garnitúra gumit, érdemes kicsit utána nézni, hogy kiknek ajánlott igazán. Mit mondanak a tesztek? A gumiabroncsakciok.hu oldal szerint érdemes figyelembe venni a különböző tesztek eredményeit is. Az ADAC tesztek Európa legnagyobb klubja által készülnek el, ahol minden évben több abroncsot vizsgálnak meg. A pontozás konkrét és fontos szempontok alapján történik, figyelik az irányíthatóságot, és ellenőrzik a gumi tulajdonságát vizes és száraz úton. Azonban minden egyes év bizonyítja, hogy tökéletes abroncs egyszerűen nem létezik! Lehet, hogy egy márka nagyon jól teljesít a havas körülmények között, azonban kevésbé lesz jó a száraz úton és fordítva. Tavaly több nagy név is megjelent a listán, mint például a Continental AllSeasonContact vagy az Uniroyal AllSeasonExpert 2. Utóbbi például kifejezetten jó eredményeket ért el a nedves utakon, azonban lényegesen gyengébben teljesített a szárazon. Ha azonban arra gondolunk, hogy nem Anglia esős övezetében élünk, akkor lehet, hogy inkább másik lehetőség után nézünk. A tavalyi nyertesek a Bridgestone Weather Control A005 és a Michelin Criss-Climate + abroncsok lettek. Nem véletlen, hogy nagy márkákat találunk a lista élén, mivel nekik van elegendő technológiai tudásuk és pénzük ahhoz, hogy folyamatosan fejlesszék az abroncsaikat, azonban még így sem beszélhetünk tökéletes eredményről. Mind a két márka nagyszerűen teljesített száraz és nedves utakon, azonban a havas körülmények között kicsit lemaradtak a többitől. Ez mind azt bizonyítja, hogy a legnagyobb prémium márkák sem tudnak száz százaléig tökéletes eredményt produkálni. Melyiket válasszuk? Akkor melyiket válasszuk? Hát ez attól függ, hogy hol akarunk vezetni. Ha egy nagy városban

élünk, és szinte sosem megyünk ki a főútra, akkor nyugodtan válasszuk a négyévszakos abroncsokat és a spórolást. De ha olyan helyen élünk, ahol faluról falura kell mennünk, esetleg a munkánkból adódóan gyakran kell hosszabb utakat megtennünk, akkor jobb, ha mindig évszak szerint választunk. Ezáltal nem spóroljuk meg a gumik árát, de biztosan eljutunk az úti célunkig.

Target Ingress

Az időjárás minden évben újabb meglepetésekkel készül, egyre többször beszélünk esőről, mint hóról, és a nyári kánikulák is elmaradnak. Vajon ez azt jelenti, hogy végre eljött a négyévszakos gumik ideje? Nézzük!

MELTSUM Summary

A nyári és a hideg hónapok során is használható, tehát nem kell szervizbe rohanni a gumicsere miatt, vagy legalábbis nem mindenkinek. A gumiabroncsakciok.hu oldal szerint érdemes figyelembe venni a tesztek eredményeit is.

XLSUM Summary

Hungary a Falcon- a benzines, a Falco- benzines.

C.5 Italian 1

Content

Il 31 marzo 1914 nasceva Octavio Paz , considerato il poeta di lingua spagnola più importante del Novecento. Fu il primo autore messicano a ricevere il premio Nobel per la Letteratura . Per celebrarlo nell' anniversario della nascita abbiamo scelto una sua poesia Tra l'andarsene e il restare , contenuta nella raccolta Albero interiore (1976-1987) edita in Italia da Garzanti nel volume (Il fuoco di ogni giorno , 1992, trad. di Ernesto Franco). La poesia di Octavio Paz è carica di simboli. Le parole evocano legami e, come in un quadro surrealista, rimandano ad altro. Nulla è quel che sembra e anche la pittoresca descrizione di un tramonto in realtà allude a una dimensione più profonda che va oltre la superficie piana delle cose. Scopriamo testo, analisi e commento della poesia dell'autore premio Nobel. Tra l'andarsene e il restare di Octavio Paz: testo Tra l'andarsene e il restare di Octavio Paz: analisi La poesia è strutturata in otto strofe composte di due versi ciascuna, non ci sono rime ma solo assonanze. Tra l'andarsene e il restare vuole esprimere una dimensione fondamentale nella vita delle persone che è il tempo . Nella lirica infatti vengono rappresentati due tipi di tempo: il primo fa riferimento a tutto ciò che è misurabile, oggettivo (come la lunghezza del giorno, Ndr) mentre il secondo è soggettivo (scandito dal battito nella tempia dell'uomo, Ndr). Il titolo stesso della poesia Tra l'andarsene e il restare fa riferimento a una condizione in bilico tra passato e futuro, che sembra eludere il momento presente -

che è l'attimo del dubbio per eccellenza - nella sua brevità. I primi versi descrivono un tramonto che si riflette su un lago. L'Io lirico che osserva la scena ne è rapito, ma allo stesso tempo consapevole della sua estraneità a quanto sta osservando. Il mondo esterno è vicino, eppure pare irraggiungibile: segue una strofa i cui versi sembrano in perfetta antitesi tra loro e si riflettono in un gioco di specchi "tutto è visibile/tutto è elusivo"; "tutto è vicino/tutto è intoccabile". La luce esterna proietta un'ombra sul tavolo della casa dalla quale lo spettatore anonimo osserva il tramonto. Allora il focus si sposta lentamente sui pensieri dell'uomo, esprimendo i suoi pensieri. L'uomo che osserva il tramonto sente che sta invecchiando mentre osserva il sole che scompare spegnendo il giorno. Il sole svanisce, ma l'uomo resta e contempla questo cambiamento totale senza neppure muoversi. "Io resto e me ne vado", osserva l'uomo colpito da una folgorazione che non riguarda solo lui, ma l'intera specie umana. "Sono una pausa" con questa affermazione l'Io lirico sembra alludere alla sua condizione esistenziale presente, in perenne bilico tra passato e futuro. Il tramonto è già passato e all'uomo rimane il ricordo del sole, perché la sua memoria riesce a catturare ogni cambiamento trasformandolo in un'istantanea. Tra l'andarsene e il restare di Octavio Paz: commento La poesia di Octavio Paz è metafisica, sembra evocare i contorni surrealisti di un quadro di Magritte. Il lettore, così come l'osservatore di un dipinto, sembra essere deputato all'osservazione, spinto sulla soglia tra realtà e rappresentazione. Nella lirica di Paz, così come in una celebre tela di Magritte intitolata La condizione umana (1933), viene raffigurata un'atmosfera sospesa in cui i confini tra ciò che l'occhio vede e il mondo effettivo appaiono labili e indefiniti. Magritte commentava il suo dipinto dicendo che vediamo il mondo come al di fuori di noi anche se in realtà è solo frutto d'una rappresentazione mentale che creiamo dentro di noi. Allo stesso modo Octavio Paz nella sua poesia Tra l'andarsene e il restare coglie un momento mentale: l'attimo del presente eterno, in cui l'Io lirico sembra assentarsi dal mondo esterno che intanto oscilla imperturbabile nel suo quieto via vai. C'è questo scollamento tra quando accade all'esterno e il pulsare del sangue nella mente dell'uomo che sembra scandire un tempo altro, il tempo breve della vita. L'andarsene e il restare sono infatti, a ben guardare, i due antipodi della condizione umana: la vita e la morte, due stati dell'essere sui quali non abbiamo scelta. Octavio Paz in questa lirica dà voce al pensiero esistenzialista. Anche se i tramonti, ovvero i giorni, passano e corrono, l'uomo rimane come una pausa nel lungo cammino dell'eternità. Attraverso una poesia l'autore premio Nobel fotografa la condizione umana. E lo fa con il surrealismo tipico della pittura di Magritte, quindi accostando tra loro gli oggetti e mostrando un paesaggio che non è quel che sembra. Tra l'andarsene e il restare non è che, in fondo, che la visione evocata dalla contemplazione di un tramonto che scolora nelle acque del lago diventando metafora del tempo.

Target Ingress

In occasione dell'anniversario della nascita del poeta messicano Octavio Paz, vi proponiamo una sua bella poesia dal titolo "Tra l'andarsene e il restare". Scopriamo testo e analisi del componimento.

MELTSUM Summary

Il 31 marzo 1914 nasceva Octavio Paz, il primo autore messicano a ricevere il premio Nobel per la Letteratura. Per celebrarlo abbiamo scelto una sua poesia Tra l'andarsene e il restare, contenuta nella raccolta *Albero interiore* edita in Italia da Garzanti.

XLSUM Summary

Octavio Paz , Premio Nobel per la Letteratura, nasce a partir del 31 marzo 1914.

C.6 Italian 2

Content

È considerata una delle più grandi ballerine di danza classica del ventunesimo secolo. Donna di stile, di classe e dal talento ineguagliabile tanto che nel 1981 il *New York Times* ha definito l'ètoile la "prima ballerina assoluta". Carla Fracci ha segnato un'epoca, ha avuto una carriera luminosa, piena di successi e di tanti riconoscimenti. Non ha brillato solo alla Scala di Milano, ma anche a Roma, a Napoli e a Londra. È morta il 27 maggio del 2021 all'età di 84 anni nella sua casa di Milano. Il suo mito, però, è ancora vivo e vegeto. Ricordare Carla Fracci è un dovere. Ci pensa Rai Uno in un film tv a lei dedicato che arriva sulla prima rete il 5 dicembre. Con lei anche il pop stava sulle punte Presentato già in anteprima alla Scala e l'8, il 9 e il 10 novembre in alcuni cinema d'Italia, ora la fiction ispirata alla vita della ballerina arriva in tv e in prima serata. A dirigere il progetto c'è Emanuele Imbucci, e alla sceneggiatura c'è Fabio Scamoni e Graziano Diana. Il film che si intitola semplicemente *Carla* è un adattamento di "Passo dopo passo – la mia storia", biografia ufficiale della Fracci edita da Mondadori. La storia inizia nel 1944 nei meandri della campagna lombarda. L'Italia è sconvolta dal terrore del Secondo conflitto mondiale e, per trovare rifugio dagli orrori della guerra, una giovane Carla Fracci si rifugia dei suoi sogni da bambina. Resta così affascinata dal volo di una libellula che si posa su un ruscello che, una volta adulta, decide di intraprendere gli studi di danza classica. Il racconto poi compie un balzo in avanti di ventisei anni in cui si conosce Carla all'apice della sua bellezza e bravura. Alessandra Mastronardi qui regala un volto umanissimo all'ètoile. Addio a Carla Fracci, regina italiana della danza La ballerina, spinta da Rudolf Nureyev, si prepara a una nuova sfida. Ha solo cinque giorni di tempo per prepararsi allo Schiaccianoci. Nonostante le difficoltà, Carla accetta comunque la sfida e, in un gioco di flashback tra passato e

presente, si ricostruisce l'immagine di una donna di spettacolo unica nel suo genere, l'unica che si è guadagnata il titolo di miglior artista al mondo. La Mastronardi, famosa per aver interpretato su Rai Uno il personaggio de L'Allieva, è celebre per i Cesaroni ma anche per I Medici e Master Of None. Con lei ci sono anche Leo Dussolier, Stefano Rossi Giornani, e Elena Cotta. Oltre che in tv, la fiction su Carla sarà disponibile in streaming su Rai Play.

Target Ingress

La vita di Carla Fracci tra storia e mito. In tv c'è la biografia della ballerina più famosa al mondo, interpretata da una magnetica Alessandra Mastronardi

MELTSUM Summary

Carla Fracci è una delle più grandi ballerine di danza classica del ventunesimo secolo. Il suo mito, però, è ancora vivo e vegeto

XLSUM Summary

Carla Fracci è famosa.